

Booklet 1

Researching Territorial Accumulation

2024

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Cover photo: CONTESTED_TERRITORY researchers in dialogue with urban spring water washerwomen. Pasankerí neighborhood, La Paz, Bolivia. Photograph by Jhaquelin Dávalos, 2024.

How to cite this document

CONTESTED_TERRITORY Network (2024). Researching Territorial Accumulation. Booklet 1.

2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 873082. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Executive summary

This booklet deals with the empirical research conducted by the CONTESTED_TERRITORY network between January 2022 and July 2024. It shows the project's contributions to the production of bottom-up scientific models capable of combining different theoretical lenses and methodological perspectives, with the aim of challenging conventional discourses on territorial development in the midst of the current global ecological crisis. This has meant privileging and centralising the knowledge, research strategies, community initiatives and political demands of local communities and groups whose ways of knowing and doing have challenged the epistemic and methodological models that have produced cycles of exploitation, dispossession, displacement and appropriation.

In line with the objectives of CONTESTED_TERRITORY, the booklet foregrounds the theoretical underpinnings, data collection techniques and research findings, describing how they approach the ongoing territorial transformations caused by the processes of capital accumulation from the point of view of the communities and groups that contest them. In this sense, it presents 21 concrete experiences of territorial accumulation in Europe and Latin America, based on a series of field research activities, including quantitative surveys, interviews, comparative analysis, participatory methods, as well as audiovisual and documentary methods.

Based on the diversity of strategies, actors and economic sectors involved in processes of territorial accumulation, the detailed experiences of territorial accumulation critically approach the knowledge production and methodologies that underpin the discourses, policies and governance schemes defined by the established narratives of infinite economic growth and sustainable development. As described throughout the booklet, this has meant examining urban, peri-urban and rural territories, describing the effects of territorial accumulation in indigenous communities, low- and middle-income sectors of urban centres and peasant communities, individualising the dynamics of capitalist accumulation and the actors involved in enabling or contesting it.

The empirical research summarised in this booklet emerges from the objectives and work packages that have thematically organised the project, specifically Work Package 3 and Task 3.4.

Introduction

This booklet has been produced as part of CONTESTED_TERRITORY, an international, cross-sectoral network involving academic and non-academic organisations from Latin America and Europe. The network aims to co-produce alternatives to conventional knowledge and traditional research models by problematising the concepts and research practices that underpin discourses, policies and governance schemes related to territorial development, as defined by models of infinite economic growth and sustainable development.

Taking this as a starting point, the CONTESTED_TERRITORY network of researchers has undertaken two simultaneous exercises. On the one hand, to critically reflect on the legacies of imperialism/colonialism in the classifications, representations, languages and power relations that constitute the theoretical and empirical knowledge produced by universities, research associations, research centres or think tanks. On the other hand, to unlearn the principles that tend to fragment, essentialise and universalise conventional research methodologies that have historically legitimised global processes of epistemic extractivism and territorial accumulation.

In contrast to perspectives that assume research as a set of neutral and passive procedures oriented towards the search for knowledge or objective truths, the CONTESTED_TERRITORY network understands

research as a set of open, fluid and situated practices that intertwine, articulate and open dialogues and exchanges between experiences and knowledge, recognising that only plural and inclusive research can take into account different spatial, territorial, climatic and social injustices. Thus, this approach does not aim at isolated and sufficient interpretations in themselves, but at the production of knowledge capable of generating ruptures with these strategies and reclaiming common ontological and epistemological futures.

These knowledges appear as emancipatory possibilities towards other senses of the world, collectively conceiving conceptual and methodological horizons that can show how research processes constitute sites of contestation by denouncing the strategies and violence inherent in modern/colonial analysis. At the same time, these possibilities can describe and even carry out actions based on the principles of reciprocity and collaboration, because they are committed to confronting the global threats to the reproduction of life caused by the crisis of the capitalist world ecology.

In this context, the use of the term territorial accumulation occurs in contexts where the co-production of situated knowledge and collective actions aim to link epistemological perspectives that are ethically and politically committed to unravelling the conditions of the current crisis, as well as to relate to and imagine (other) knowledges and (other) spatialities.

What do we mean by territorial accumulation? ¹

Located in the crisis of the capitalist world-ecology, which brings together the cyclical contradictions of capital accumulation, aggravated by the deepening subsumption of labour/energy to capital, the concept of territorial accumulation confronts and attempts to denaturalise the so-called 'developmentalist consensus' anchored in both neoliberalism and progressivism, systems that reflect the technical-scientific rationality of modernity/coloniality.

As a consequence of the crisis of the world ecology, the current articulations between capital, territory, nature and power have triggered complex transformations in the dynamics, relations and contradictions of the production of the web of life in the capitalocene, especially in the environments produced to serve these dynamics. The complexity of these articulations suggests the need to generate relational and pluriversal alternatives at the intersection of thought and action, interwoven with the diverse knowledge and practices of local communities and groups.

The latter have both examined and challenged the contradictions of capital accumulation, the processes of

extraction and appropriation of cheap nature, and the effects of uneven geographical development.

The constant mutations in the cycles of capitalist production reveal the diversity of strategies, scales, territories and sectors through which life tends to be totally subordinated to the dictates of capital accumulation. As empirical research inspired by the concept of territorial accumulation shows, the imperatives of the capitalist system of production, such as the absorption of surplus capital, the maintenance of an increasing rate of profit and productivity, also affect the micro-elements of the reproduction of human life and the constant fragmentation of the metabolism between human and non-human life, a direct consequence of the expansion of the frontiers of exploitation and appropriation.

[1] The discussion and construction of the notion of territorial accumulation is an objective of CONTESTED_TERRITORY. What we present here is based precisely on the work of the Working Paper 1 "Analytical Categories of Territorial Accumulation", the Working Paper 2 "Comparative Critical Policy Analysis applied to Territorial Accumulation", and the Dossier on Territorial Accumulation under preparation.

Given the extent to which these processes shape the conditions and rhythms of life, the term 'territorial accumulation' attempts to separate itself from those critical currents of thought that aim to produce master theories or narratives that tend to synthesise, totalise and universalise theoretical and methodological approaches to the fabric of life under capitalism. Rather, territorial accumulation is a conceptual framework that makes sense when understood in three ways:

- 1 As a **broad horizon of interpretation** that privileges and incorporates other knowledge marginalised by the power relations of hegemonic Western knowledge,
- 2 as a **theoretical and methodological strategy** that makes it possible to identify and examine the different logics of capital accumulation in the production of territories, and
- 3 as a **research tool**, in that it encourages the use of both conventional and experimental methodologies to address the complex dynamics of territories.

However, by asking how the production and reproduction of life can be thought and interpreted in multiple, complex, uncertain and contradictory ways, without totalising and without claiming to be fully comprehensible, this triple way of understanding territorial accumulation questions the conditions of its own possibility. Thus, empirical research that seeks to approach the processes of territorial accumulation does not exhaust itself in any conceptual apparatus and actively renounces objectivity and essentialism.

On the other hand, the notion of territorial accumulation investigates the relationship between human beings and nature, focusing on examining the constant reduction of life to the valorisation of capital and the commodification of every aspect of life as facts firmly anchored in a set of discourses, representations and practices about nature. As a strategy and tool, this theoretical-practical framework allows us to rethink alternatives to life as determined by capital, to explore the possibility of other designs and protocols that are not based on separation and opposition, nor on domination and appropriation.

What is the content of this booklet?

The theoretical assemblages outlined in CONTESTED_TERRITORY – territorial accumulation and territories in dispute – propose a consciously open and interpretative approach to achieve a thorough understanding of the mechanisms of conflict and political disputes in the production and appropriation of the different spaces and knowledge anchored in territory. This booklet aims to show the diversity of territories, strategies, scales and economic sectors from which processes of territorial accumulation have been identified through the mobilities, meetings, projects, activities and collaborations promoted by CONTESTED_TERRITORY between Latin America and Europe.

Throughout this booklet, the reader will be able to navigate through 21 research experiences that not only combine different empirical research methodologies, but also incorporate other knowledges and theoretical perspectives. These experiences cover urban, peri-urban and rural areas; they describe the effects of territorial accumulation in indigenous communities, in peasant communities and in low- and middle-income sectors of urban centres; and they involve different types of actors: local/community, state, corporate, transnational, among others.

The aim is to make this set of case studies available to students, teachers, collectives, territorially based social and community organisations, activists, artists, cultural managers and other interested actors, revealing the spatial, social, environmental, economic and political impacts produced by territorial accumulation. Moreover, in each of these research experiences it is possible to observe multiple participatory processes, facilitated by the use of methodological strategies that cross traditional and experimental methodologies: reviewing multiple sources of printed and audiovisual material; interviews; participation in activism and debates; knowledge exchange with local actors; workshops; walks; performances; observation and listening.

Given the implications of systematising heterogeneous constellations, this booklet adopts a typology to classify territorial accumulation processes:

- Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources
- Urbanisation, redevelopment, large projects and infrastructures
- Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds, tourism, gentrification
- Commodification and neo-liberalisation of production and trade circuits and popular markets
- Commodification of public space and the commons.

Case 1

Extractivism and environmental violence in the Ecuadorian Amazon²

Keywords

Amazonía

Oil extractivism

Residual urbanisation

Dependency and decoloniality

Climate injustice

Type of accumulation

Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The process of urbanisation in the Ecuadorian Amazon began with the oil boom in the late 1960s. The concessionaire, Texaco, built the first well and the first station in the Amazon, in Lago Agrio, now the largest city in the Ecuadorian Amazon, with more than 100,000 inhabitants. Since then, these infrastructures have been a factor of territorial dispossession and pollution, due to the emissions from the lighters and the constant spillage of oil, which causes serious health problems for the local population.

In 1992, social pressure forced Texaco to leave the country, in the midst of a lawsuit brought by 30,000 peasants and indigenous people from the northern Ecuadorian Amazon, which even led to the company's name being changed to Chevron Corporation. However, the Ecuadorian state continued to concede oil blocks to new transnational companies, and more oil pipelines and stations were built in Lago Agrio and throughout the northern Amazon, while the less profitable ones were closed.

Oil well Lago Agrio 39 located in the 25 de Febrero neighborhood of the city of Lago Agrio. Environmental violence against the population is multiple: dispute over water, water pollution, noise, gas emissions, among others. Photograph by Christian Serrano, 2021.

In 2007, a period of recentralisation began in the country, with attempts to nationalise oil activity through contract renegotiation processes, but at the same time an expansion towards the east with the Yasuní-ITT block (for the exploration of the Ishpingo-Tambococho-Tiputini wells), which the organised communities managed to legally stop in 2023.

The research carried out in the Ecuadorian Amazon problematises precisely the link between the forms of capitalist accumulation of extractivism and the type of urbanisation it generates, not only mining and oil extractivism, but also agro-industry and tourism. It examines oil extractivist urbanisation, infrastructural processes, processes of gentrification from the extractive peripheries, that is, the set of actions recognised as "oil violence", in which territorial accumulation is the macro-process that underlies unequal development.

Amazonian urbanisation, as an expression of the phenomenon of extended urbanisation generated by the global production model, is studied in a situated way, seeking to investigate the complex ways in which spaces, rights and policies are contested in the Amazonian territory, seen from the role of the state and from different subjectivities.

Here we analyse the empirical work carried out in a series of researches and presented in different academic articles, with a focus on "A climate justice approach to urbanisation processes in the South" and "The oil axis in Ecuador": The oil axis in Ecuador" and "Decolonising urban studies from the Amazon: indigenous practices to contest planetary urbanisation".

In the first case, oil extractivism in the Ecuadorian Amazon is examined through an analysis of extended urbanisation and uneven development, in dialogue with Latin American dependency theory as a framework for decolonising urban studies and as an extension of the articulation between urban studies and political ecology.

Territory

Ecuador
Amazonian provinces

[2] This review is based on research by Manuel Bayón of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany; Gustavo Durán of the Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO Ecuador); and Melissa Moreano of the Universidad Andina Simón Bolívar (UASB Ecuador).

The research builds on contributions from the literature on environmental justice and urbanisation in the global South, which shows that the distribution of environmental and infrastructure services is unequal, operates on the basis of certain economic income and race/ethnicity characteristics, and is a tool of social stratification.

Focusing on the social production of extractivism-related urban space in Ecuador along the oil pipeline that crosses the country from east to west, from the extraction zone in the Amazon to the export port on the Pacific, the analysis shows that popular and racialised communities have very little capacity to manage or cope with climate injustice, i.e. the concrete risks or consequences of pollution, unhealthy temperatures, floods and landslides generated by extractivist urbanisation.

The research identifies uneven geographical development and dependency as constitutive of climate injustices associated with urbanisation. From this perspective, cities are not seen as an isolated element, but as a specific moment in the configuration of inequalities, among which climate injustices fuelled by oil extraction stand out.

The focus on climate injustices allows the understanding of urbanisation processes to be incorporated into climate thinking, not only by considering how cities will transition to sustainable models as independent entities, but also by looking at the process of urbanisation itself beyond the notion of urban transition, focusing instead on its inherent dynamics of uneven development. The insatiable appetite for fossil-fuel based capital

accumulation, this research concludes, leads to the constant creation of new infrastructures that make cities ever more remote and crowded, leading to ever greater dispossession and pushing particularly popular and racialised communities into precarious urban peripheries.

In the second case, the research seeks to challenge the approaches of planetary urbanisation from the analysis of the territorial configuration of urban Amazonian subjects, for which it carries out a multi-scalar analysis situated by contrasting the visions of planetary urbanisation with those of the practices, perceptions and spatialities of social actors in the face of the great flows of capital in the Ecuadorian Amazon.

The authors argue that indigenous cultural strategies and practices have the capacity to limit the violence generated by extractivism in the Amazon. Among these strategies, they identify a variety of forms of appropriation and adaptation to the process of urbanisation, refuting the argument that urbanisation is opposed to indigenous territoriality. In many cases, negotiations and agreements with public institutions mediate their inclusion in economic development; in others, access to social housing programmes justifies historical struggles to exercise their citizenship rights.

This research is based on the assumption that space is the product of unequal power relations, that 'the city' is neither given, static nor delimited, and that urbanisation is a dynamic process linked to the needs of capitalism. In other words, the very constitution of cities is based on local, contextual conditions.

Multiscalar methodological strategy: Geo-historical and ethnographic approach

In the research "A climate justice approach to urbanisation processes in the South: The Oil Axis in Ecuador", which sought to extend the analysis beyond the view of the delimited city and to understand urbanisation as a process, the methodological strategy was based on a transductive research design, using cartographic, comparative and mobile ethnographic methods. The mapping used secondary sources such as the database of the Military Geographical Institute of Ecuador (IGM) and the Amazonian Extended Urbanisation Database developed by FLACSO-Ecuador. Between 2019 and 2022, GPS points were recorded during ten tours of these areas, identifying the places where oil exploitation has triggered increased urbanisation in recent decades.

A spatial-historical methodological approach was used to understand the structure of the territory, how different actors have spatialised their lives throughout history, and the territorial powers in dispute. The authors carried out a continuous observation and reflection on the spatial modifications produced by different megaprojects and infrastructures in the Amazon region, opting for an analysis of multiple spatial scales.

Five scales formed the basis of the inductive exercise:

1 The scale of the extractive enclave

Tiputini, the most recent enclave resulting from oil exploitation in the Yasuni-ITT block.

2 The inland waterway oil transport stop

Providencia, the river port where the infrastructure and materials necessary for exploitation are shipped.

Flares burning gas in the Shushufindi oil field, near the cantonal capital of the same name, which operate 24 hours a day. Photograph by Manuel Bayón, 2016.

3 The size of the oil service

El Coca, capital of the province of Orellana, the first city to participate in this process.

5 The scale of the export refinery

the city of Esmeraldas, the refinery where the pipeline arrives and the port where the oil leaves the country.

4 The size of the rent capital

Quito, the national capital, which participates in oil revenues and is the hub of the pipeline.

Once the sites of analysis and the scales they represent had been defined, qualitative fieldwork was carried out to deepen our understanding of disputes over urbanisation and climate injustice.

Through 20 in-depth interviews, ethnographic analysis was used to understand how people inhabit space, what their key political demands are, and how new infrastructure generates or transforms subjectivities. These interviews were conducted between 2019 and 2022 with local planners and leaders in each of the analysis sites, in order to provide an in-depth explanation of the three variables of analysis that emerged from the theoretical framework: the drivers of sprawling urbanisation, the basis of environmental inequalities, and the struggles for better conditions.

Pipes transporting oil extracted in the 25 de Febrero neighborhood in the city of Lago Agrio. Photograph by Manuel Bayón, 2021.

Residual urbanisation as opposed to planetary urbanisation

In the research "Decolonising urban studies from the Amazon: indigenous practices to contest planetary urbanisation", the multi-scalar approach was applied to specifically study indigenous conflicts and disputes in the face of Amazonian urbanisation from three scales: regional, local and every day.

The regional scale was applied around the main axes of urbanisation, in order to understand the development and transformation of urban forms and their responses from a perspective that spans long historical periods and provides information on how the territory has been structured and its actors spatialised over time. At this level, the work consisted in reviewing the historical, quantitative and qualitative statistical-territorial documentation of the socio-economic structures and the actions and strategies of the different actors, which made it possible to define eight communities or neighbourhoods for the analysis of indigenous territorialities and spatialities.

Through the local scale, it was possible to find out how indigenous and mestizo actors understand the city, their displacement towards new infrastructures and the obstacles they face in building their neighbourhoods. This work is based on 30 in-depth interviews conducted in the second half of 2021.

On a daily basis, the empirical work consisted of participant observation in these neighbourhoods and communities in order to understand the ways of living, mobility and transport, the conditions of access to basic services and the housing situation.

The systematisation of the knowledge acquired at these three levels led to an analysis of the cases and the construction of a typology of the ways in which indigenous territorialities mobilise to contest the central spaces of colonial urbanisation processes:

1. Adapting to the arrival of urban dynamics.
2. Obtaining state-produced housing.
3. Establishing their own forms of urbanisation to avoid territorial dispossession.
4. Urbanising already peri-urban areas under the tension of their transformation into urban private property, configuring new urban spaces with indigenous logic.

This diversity of practices allows us to affirm that in the Ecuadorian Amazon, in the light of the observation of forms of urban indigenous territoriality, planetary urbanisation has the potential to become residual, with greater power of indigenous organisation in the urban sphere.

Participating node

- Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales (FLACSO), Ecuador

Further information

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- "Agro-industrial urbanisation in Santo Domingo", in the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation. <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/santo-domingo/>
- "Contestaciones a la contaminación petrolera en Lago Agrio", in the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation. <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/lago-agrio/>

Other related activities

- Online seminar "Violencia extractivista y contestaciones territoriales en la urbanización (pan)amazónica". Flacso Quito, November 27, 2020. <https://www.contested-territories.net/seminario-violencia-extractivista-y-contestaciones-territoriales-en-la-urbanizacion-panamazonica/>
- Face-to-face meeting "Mapoteca Amazónica" in Lago Agrio, Ecuador, January 2023.
- Face-to-face meeting "Encuentro Diálogos Sur-Sur 2 / Mapoteca 2" in La Paz, Bolivia, March-April 2024.

Case 2

Transnational oil presence in Esmeraldas, Ecuador³

Keywords

Esmeraldas

Oil extractivism

Marginalisation

Inequalities

Risk

Type of accumulation

Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

Due to its geographical location in the Pacific lowlands and its natural and cultural conditions, the city of Esmeraldas in Ecuador concentrates a large number of processes of territorial accumulation. Historically, the different waves of extractivism can be linked to the functions that capital-based production has assigned to Esmeraldas since colonial rule: "the banana city", "the river city", "the oil city" and "the tourist city". Throughout its history, each of these functions has played a crucial role in the geographical, political and symbolic construction of the Ecuadorian state.

The extractivist wave of the "oil city" has left its mark throughout the province. Currently, the processes of accumulation are linked to the refining and export of oil as a result of the so-called "oil boom" of the 1970s, following the discovery of oil deposits in the eastern part of the country. This dynamic accelerated the country's economic growth, attracted foreign capital and companies, (ii) increased the amount of money in circulation and (iii) implied the construction of infrastructure. In addition, the influx of oil revenues had political and institutional effects: on the one hand, social programmes were implemented (education, health, housing and the adaptation of basic services), economic and military programmes (the purchase of weapons during the dictatorship of Guillermo Rodríguez Lara), and on the other hand, state institutions were created to serve the oil industry.

After the oil boom, the "banana city" was replaced by the "oil city": (i) pipelines crossed the territory of Esmeraldas, (ii) a refinery was built south of the city, (iii) pumping and storage infrastructure was installed, (iv) the port became Ecuador's only outlet for oil, and (v) oil tankers became a common sight from the beaches. These transformations included the territories of Esmeraldas in the country's development strategies and they became contributors to the Gross Domestic Product with a high per capita income compared to other regions of the country.

Composition of the population in Esmeraldas

Afro-descendants	53.8%
Mestizos	39.5%
Whites	1.6%
Indigenous people	3.4%
Montubius	1.7%

Source: INEC, 2023.

Territory

Ecuador
Esmeraldas province

Rise of the Teaone River, at the foot of the thermoelectric plant in Esmeraldas, in the 50 Casas neighborhood. Photograph by GADME, 2016.

[3] This review is based on research by Julien Rebotier of the Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), France; Pascale Metzger of the Institut de recherche pour le développement (IRD), France; and Patrick Pigeon of the University of Savoie, France.

Thermolectric plant of Esmeraldas located on the banks of the Teaone River, photographed from the 50 Casas neighborhood. Photograph by Julien Rebotier, 2017.

Despite its consolidation as a region of national importance and the concentration of large amounts of capital, the territories of Esmeraldas are at a crossroads for the implementation of economic activities based mainly on the extraction of natural resources. In Esmeraldas it is possible to find heavy infrastructure (oil pipelines, thermolectric generators, pipelines, port, refinery) and urban infrastructure linked to oil exploitation (neighbourhoods built for oil workers and housing estates). However, there are major deficiencies in water and electricity supplies, housing conditions, health care and, in general, the quality of life for most of the population. For this reason, Esmeraldas has been described as a 'marginal', 'forgotten', 'poor' and 'vulnerable' city.

It is no coincidence that Esmeraldas is perceived in this way. These characteristics reflect the relationship between oil extraction and the lives of the diverse communities that inhabit these territories. Within this relationship, national and local governments have systematically prioritised the demands of oil extraction over the needs and well-being of these communities. According to the research that informs this report, oil extractivism is directly implicated in the creation and intensification of risks, the degradation of air and water quality, and the deepening of marginalisation processes in Esmeraldas.

These issues mobilised a series of investigations aimed at producing "attempts" to interpret the discourses and practices, as well as the scientific data and documents, that normalise or make invisible the paradoxes and tensions within the territories of Esmeraldas. Once the empirical work had been carried out, the methodological strategy for the analysis was to group the results in a triangular format – thematic, problematic, interpretative – which, in addition to helping to classify the empirical work, allowed us to reveal the research techniques and make critical contributions to the processes of territorial accumulation through the prism of risk and marginality.

El Manglar neighborhood, in the estuary of the Esmeraldas River, just a few meters from downtown Esmeraldas; stilt houses, very common on the coast, are usually built on wooden pilings. Photograph by Pascale Metzger, 2018.

Thematic triangle

City, oil and risks

Situating the production processes of territories through the prism of risk and understanding risks from the perspective of the interactions between knowledge-governance-petroleum-territory are two important contributions of the research reviewed in this case. As they point out, Esmeraldas is one of the provinces of Ecuador most exposed to natural and human (anthropogenic) hazards and risks. Most of these risks are directly related to oil exploitation and its impact on the territories (deforestation, air and water pollution, ecocide, flooding and human settlements in earthquake and tsunami zones).

National and local governments have attempted to manage the risks by generating certain knowledge about them and by taking measures. Among these measures, the compensation model stands out, especially during the years of Rafael Correa's presidency (2007-2017), when millions of dollars were allocated to the province of Esmeraldas and energy companies to compensate the territories for their extractive activities, but the threats did not diminish or were mismanaged.

To determine the extent of compensation and its impact on the risk situation in Esmeraldas, part of the empirical work (Rebotier, 2023) analysed five databases related to compensation programmes, four of which correspond to the main energy companies: Empresa Pública de Hidrocarburos del Ecuador (EP Petroecuador), Oleoducto de Crudos Pesados (OCP), Empresa Pública Flota Petrolera Ecuatoriana (FLOPEC) and Corporación Eléctrica del Ecuador (CELEC). This required the creation of a proprietary database with refined information based on the compensation period (2009-2018) and its explicit link to Esmeraldas. At the same time, 5 interviews and data collection were carried out in different meetings with 25 people who were in contact with the territories under scrutiny.

Problematic triangle

knowledge, marginality and value production

Esmeraldas refers to a specific process of territorial accumulation. Its territories have been shaped and defined by oil-based extractivism, which has allowed the production of value or profit through the marginalisation of local communities and the subjugation of these territories to the strategies and designs of national development. Development, in approaches that privilege economic growth through the extraction of natural resources, tends to reinforce the accumulation-marginalisation binomial, assuming the latter as a permanent condition and the sole cause of the lack of information on the risks and quality of life of the inhabitants. Although marginality is essential for the production of value (Rebotier, 2023), it is not a starting point but an outcome historically constructed by extractivist practices, cultural stereotypes and scientific theories.

In order to reconstruct the history of Esmeraldas's marginality and position its role in the processes that have contributed to the expansion of oil extractivist activities, the research techniques used in the above studies were:

25 Structured interviews
with land managers, land management practitioners and researchers in Esmeraldas and Quito

50 Semi structured interviews
with personnel from different public and private companies in the oil sector in Esmeraldas

Consultation of official archives
in Quito and Esmeraldas

Analysis of historical chronicles
on Esmeraldas

Review of documents
from various local, national and international institutions of field trips

Cartoons published in the cultural magazine *Meridiano Negro*, which had among its editor Nelson Estupiñán Bass (Ecuadorian poet, essayist, and journalist who depicted the life of the Afro-Ecuadorian population). *Meridiano Negro*, 1980.

Front page of *El Universo* newspaper after an oil spill in the Esmeraldas River caught fire (February 28, 1998).

Interpretative triangle

power, history and scale

Through the use of such techniques, these studies have been able to approach an understanding of territories by considering three related variables: power, history and scale, and two prisms: risk and marginality. This methodological combination has established a relationship between territorial accumulation and marginalisation, as well as between the production of territory and risk, which in the case of Esmeraldas is mainly the extraction of natural resources, especially oil.

In this sense, this research questions the common ground from which other studies approach extractivist processes and development discourses, focusing instead on the impact of these extractive processes on local communities, the risks they generate and the negative consequences of the mitigation models that are applied in the face of their effects, even when these are formulated by national governments that invoke a more equitable distribution of oil revenues.

Thus, the attempts to interpret the data obtained problematise the so-called "compensatory state",

a strategy used by various governments, especially Correa's, to mitigate the negative effects of the exploitation of natural resources.

According to these studies, this strategy, although it involves the investment of millions of dollars in the territories of Esmeraldas, does not take into account the needs of the communities affected by oil extraction; on the contrary, it transforms the urban space in a way that can generate risks for human and non-human life in Esmeraldas, delegitimises local governments, ignores the processes of the communities themselves, and does not improve access to services or housing.

This research shows the need to reformulate research work, to situate research objectives within the framework of demands for climate justice, and to create our own models of research that are appropriate to the histories and geographies that challenge and contest the dominant ways of producing lives and territories marked by the extraction and appropriation of natural resources.

Participating nodes

- Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), Bayonne, France
- Institut de recherche pour le développement (IRD), Paris, France
- Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales (FLACSO), Ecuador

Further information

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Case 3

The Salado Basin, Argentina, a territory dominated by the production approach⁴

Keywords

Argentine pampas

Hydrological basins

Agricultural frontier

Agro-industry

Cartographies

Type of accumulation

Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The Salado Basin is located in the Pampas region of the Province of Buenos Aires, Argentina, and covers an area of approximately 64,000 km², according to the National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA). It has numerous water sources and other features that, together with cultural and historical definitions, have oriented the area towards cattle production. However, since the 1970s, the expansion of the agricultural frontier, with soya as the main crop, has changed the productive vocation of the region, orienting it towards soya monoculture, which has been resisted by some local communities who have tried to maintain cattle farming, not only for productive reasons, but also for cultural and scenic reasons.

In this space, academics, environmental organisations, producers, residents and public institutions of technology, production and infrastructure construct ideas and produce maps through which they reflect a framework of landscape, environment, production and history from their visions of this territory. Thus, the systematisation of cartographies produced around the same space in the Salado Basin shows different spatial boundaries and denominations.

Three main perspectives are in tension in defining the use of land and natural resources in this basin: ecological, hydrological and productive. These are tensions between scales and interests that range from the local to the global: a) local actors have strong roots and identities linked to livestock production; b) at the provincial level, the focus has been on infrastructure planning to regulate water phenomena, especially flooding in this basin; c) at the regional level, the expansion of the agricultural frontier conditions the productive activities carried out in this territory; d) at the national level, livestock farming is present for productive and socio-cultural reasons; and e) at the global level, the visions of an international market that demands an increase in agricultural production are confronted with environmental movements that push for the preservation of the region's natural grasslands.

A systematisation of the cartographies produced on the Salado basin since 1980 shows the predominance of a productive approach, i.e. the agricultural dimension of the territory is the one that cuts across all views. Other characteristics of the basin, such as its environmental and hydrological value, are subordinated to its contribution to the productive process. Thus, over the years, infrastructural interventions have been made to regulate the climatic phenomena present in the basin, such as flooding, which can affect soybean crops.

This research analyses how the agro-export model that dominates the Argentine production matrix, specifically the production of genetically modified soya, develops processes of territorial accumulation that affect other uses and visions of the Pampean territory.

[4] This review is based on research by Julieta Monzón and Serena Olivera of the Faculty of Agronomy of the University of Buenos Aires (FAUBA), Argentina; and Julien Rebotier of the Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), France.

The empirical work consisted in the systematisation and analysis of 25 cartographies produced on the Salado Basin since 1980 and identified in different sources: technical, academic, official and popular documents. The conceptual approach and the methodological focus of the systematisation resulted from the exchange of experiences between researchers.

Participating nodes

- Centre national de la recherche scientifique, Bayonne, France
- Institut de recherche pour le développement, Paris, France
- Facultad de Agronomía de la Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina

Further information

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- "La Cuenca del Salado", in the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation. <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/la-cuenca-del-salado/>

Herding cows on horseback in the district of Azul, province of Buenos Aires, Argentina. Photograph by Julieta Monzón, 2022.

Case 4

Cartographies of the soul in the *Katsa Su*, territory of the *Awá* people in southwestern Colombia⁵

Keywords

Awá territory

Indigenous peoples

Animatic cartographies

Armed conflict

Memory

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The *Awá* are one of Colombia's 115 indigenous peoples⁶ and maintain a spiritual and cultural relationship with their territory, called *Katsa Su* in *Awapit*, their native language. This territory is a deep communicative bridge between the *Awá* and a set of energetic and biocultural codes present in the dense coastal piedmont, in the region known as the Chocó biogeographic zone, in southwestern Colombia.

In the context of the Colombian armed conflict, in a context of territorial disputes over drug trafficking, mining and the penetration of other extractive economies, the *Awá* have suffered multiple forms of violence that affect their relationship with their territory. Historically, various forms of territorial accumulation have provoked territorial usurpation, cultural uprooting, the modernisation of colonial violence and the disruption of the *Katsa Su*'s ancestral and ecosophical relationships. The tensions associated with the dynamics of the armed conflict, as well as structural violence such as economic, environmental and political suffocation, subtract from and threaten the exchanges inherent to the territories. In south-western Colombia, therefore, the armed conflict fulfils a biopolitical function of dispossession.

Recognition of community strategies for emotional mapping in the *Katsa Su* during a gathering of *Awá* women leaders. Photograph by Paula I. Guerrero, 2021.

[5] This review is based on the work of Boris Delgado of the Pontificia Javeriana University in Cali, Colombia.

[6] Colombia is inhabited by about 115 indigenous peoples of diverse origins and linguistic and cultural traditions. In the last national census of 2018, the total indigenous population reported was 1.9 million people, of which 64% inhabit 846 legalized collective territories; the rest of the population is located in urban centers or dispersed rural areas. <https://www.iwgia.org/es/colombia/5481-mi-2024-colombia.html#:~:text=En%20Colombia%20habitan%20cerca%20de,y%20tradiciones%20ling%C3%BC%C3%ADsticas%20y%20culturales>

Type of accumulation

Commodification of public space and the commons

Territorial dispossession by armed violence

The war has unfolded in a network of multicultural relations with understandings that differ from the narrative of development and extractivism. The systematisation of a complex and ever-changing violence affected the symbolic and ecosophical fields of survival. The uprooting and humanitarian crisis of the *Awá* people reveals the dramatic and arbitrary nature of the armed conflict, which is a constant dynamic of territorial usurpation.

Violence in the *Katsa Su* began to increase two decades ago, with profound humanitarian and cultural consequences; in 2009, the Colombian Constitutional Court even considered the *Awá* to be one of the ethnic groups at serious risk of physical and cultural disappearance.

One of the main consequences of the armed conflict in this territory has been the destruction of water sources, which are of great importance to their culture ("Los ríos de la memoria", a podcast on water and war).⁷

[7] "Los ríos de la memoria" is a podcast that contains stories and sonorities of the *Awá* people; the Vegas River, testimony of ancestral wealth, communicates lives, paths and stories of the Chagúí, Chimbuza, Pialapi, Pueblo Viejo and Magúí communities in the department of Nariño, in Colombia. <https://open.spotify.com/episode/OHWD9zX6kVzuZCx6YbTXnN?si=xrwU5PR6SUenxyZ75LtoOQ&nd=1>

In a participatory meeting for the construction of emotional cartographies, an alternative map to the violations of their human rights was drawn up. Community authorities, leaders and elders discussed and reflected on the need to rescue the *Katsa Su* as a sentient and binding body for the future of their communities. This sensitive experience suggests that care and reparation plans must also understand and integrate the different universes of meaning.

The situation of the *Awá* has been addressed by Colombia's comprehensive transitional justice system as part of the 2016 "Acuerdo final para la terminación del conflicto y la construcción de una paz estable y duradera" ('Final Agreement for the Termination of the Conflict and the Establishment of a Stable and Lasting Peace').⁸ In this process, the impact on the *Awá* people's territory and cosmos was perceived in a distant and different way from the traditional way in which the justice system documented the facts of violence.

When communities talk about it, an embodied, mythical and symbolic territorial vision emerges that goes beyond the expectations of the law. Through autonomous exercises, *Awá* indigenous organisations map the impact of the conflict on their territories according to what the *Katsa Su* want to express.

The products of this research have been used in public and political advocacy for the survival of the *Awá* territory, as tools to build bridges and generate urgent social dialogue on the humanitarian crisis they are experiencing. based on the communities' own interpretation of the impact of the war on their territories. This was the contribution of these communities to the Transitional Justice Reports for Macro Case O2 of the Special Justice for Peace.⁹

In order to listen to the *Katsa Su* as a spiritual corporeality, experimental encounters of community research were conducted, guided by collaborative ethnographies and situated in the biocultural references that the *Awá* attribute to their being in the territory. Symbolic anchors were articulated through bodily memories, direct experiences of war and pronouncements from the *Awá* law of origin.

The design of the meetings was based on the methodological framework of the research project "Co-creating Knowledge and Healing Memories for *Awá* Survival",¹⁰ and consisted of the use of four main resources:

- 1 Communal multisensoriality**
which consists of the articulation of sensory experiences as generators of relational knowledge in memory processes.
- 2 Corporeal and territorial mappings**
which are practices of situated knowledge that allow access to symbolic landscapes, to mobilities and transitions, to active interlocutions and negotiations between coexisting beings.
- 3 Graphic thinking**
which stimulates thought and memory processes based on the graphic and spatial representation of mythical stories, problematic situations and alternatives for the future.
- 4 Spaces for circular and biocultural listening**
which are conversational processes that bring together collective sensibilities and establish a disposition towards reflexivity and the articulation of solidarity networks of affection for the processes of memory.

Recognition of patterns of violence in the territory during a gathering of the Awá Camawari Indigenous Guard. Photograph by Boris Delgado, 2021.

Through these non-prescriptive itineraries, intersubjective constructions are achieved which, in their movement with the *Awá*'s own knowledge, can lead to a practice of healing memory.

Participating node

- Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, Cali, Colombia

Further information

- "Cartografías anímicas en el *katsa su*: pervivencia del pueblo *Awá* en medio de la guerra", in the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation. <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/katsa-su/>

[8] Agreement resulting from the Havana dialogues between delegates of the Colombian National Government and delegates of the Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia (FARC), with the mutual decision to put an end to the national armed conflict. https://www.cancilleria.gov.co/sites/default/files/Fotos2016/12.11_12016nuevoacuerdofinal.pdf

[9] In the framework of the Peace Agreement in Colombia, the Macro Case O2 is responsible for investigating serious violations of human rights and International Humanitarian Law that were allegedly committed in the municipalities of Ricaurte, Tumaco and Barbacoas in the department of Nariño by the FARC-EP and law enforcement forces between 1990 and 2016. <https://www.procuraduria.gov.co/portal/media/docs/Que-se-investiga-en-el-Caso-002.pdf>

[10] Title of the doctoral work of Boris Delgado Hernández, within the research line Social and Armed Conflicts of the doctoral training program in psychology at the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana de Cali.

Case 5

Territorial struggle of the Qom people in Argentina¹¹

Keywords

- Dispossession
- National parks
- Territorialisation
- Indigenous territory
- Natural assets

Type of accumulation

- Commodification of public space and the commons
- Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The *Qom Potae Napocna Navogoh* indigenous community in Formosa Province, Argentina, has faced various forms of territorial dispossession. The most recent of these, in 2010, was the result of the provincial state's action to build a university campus, which could not be carried out due to precautionary measures taken by the community, in addition to the road blockade that prevented access to materials.¹²

Faced with the various processes of fragmentation, nationalisation and privatisation of indigenous territories, this *Qom* community is carrying out different forms of protest, demanding the return of 26,948 hectares and autonomy to define the use of land in their territory.

The research referred to in this case is based on the notion of territorialisation, understood as the set of knowledge and actions by means of which an apparatus of power establishes a necessary relationship between a population and a geographical space, leading to a process of general reorganisation of that population (Pacheco de Oliveira, 2006). In any territorialisation process, there are hegemonic initiatives (practices, regulations, representations, discourses, etc.) that lead, by direct and/or indirect means, to the establishment of a new relationship between a population and its territory. This, in turn, involves the actions of the subjects concerned. The various policies of territorialisation carried out by the hegemonic logic, mainly of the national and provincial state, which shape the eastern part of the province of Formosa in the indigenous *Qom* territory, are an example of this.

Territories

Qom Potae Napocna community demanding their rights in a march in the city of Buenos Aires. Archive of the *Qom* community, 2011.

Figure 1. Territorial struggle of the *Qom Potae Napocna Navogoh* people. Source: L. Cardin for the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation, 2023.

[11] This review is based on the work of Lorena Cardin, researcher at the Instituto de Investigaciones en Diversidad Cultural y Procesos de Cambio (CONICET - UNRN), Argentina.

[12] The *Qom* people filed a writ of amparo that included other actors given that the territorial conflict is broader; in this appeal they denounced the authorities of the National Park, the provincial government and the Celia family (Creole) as usurpers of their territory.

Figure 1 shows (i) the territory historically inhabited by the Qom community, (ii) the territory recognised for this community by the Argentine national government in 1940, (iii) the polygon occupied by the Pilcomayo River National Park, established by national law in 1951, and (iv) the territory covered by the title granted to the community by the provincial government in 1985, namely the superimposition of "mensuras" by the state administration as a form of territorial dispossession.

March of the Qom community on the anniversary of the repression that occurred in 2010. Archive of the Qom community 2012.

The accompaniment of this problem and the struggle for territory began in 2001. In a process that has lasted more than two decades, the research also reveals the use of violence and repression as part of the strategy of dispossession. There is ample evidence of violent state action against the community. Through the use of cartography, the various actions of resistance and contestation are shown, such as the roadblocks, sit-ins and encampment of the Qom Potae Napocna Navogoh community in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires to demand the intervention of the national justice system.

From an ethnographic perspective, under what the author defines as "collaborative anthropology", an ethnographic methodology was used, consisting of extended stays in the community, participant observation, written, audio and visual records, tours of the territory, elaboration of life histories, open interviews and kinship genealogies, among others.

Cartography, as well as extensive ethnographic work, proved to be fundamental tools in demonstrating that all these 'recognitions' reflect the territorial dispossession of the Qom people, who historically occupied all these sectors, now fragmented by administrative definitions.

The participatory mapping resulted in a "map of territorial claims", which accompanied the community's lawsuit in court on two occasions, in 2018 and 2021.¹³ The researcher participated as a legal expert in both the land case and the criminal case of state repression against the community for their land claim.

Participating node

- Grupo Antropología, Ciudad y Naturaleza del Área de Estudios Urbanos de la Facultad de Ciencias Sociales. Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina

Further information

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- "Lucha territorial de la comunidad Qom Potae Napocna Navogoh", in the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation. <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/potae-napocna-navogoh/>

[13] In 2010, in the context of the road blockade carried out by the Qom community, which was protesting the beginning of the construction of the National University of Formosa's headquarters in their territory, they filed a precautionary measure to stop the construction. Two months later, it filed a writ of amparo for the territorial claim. In December 2017 the Supreme Court of Justice of the Nation (SCJN) declared its original jurisdiction and ordered that the amparo be processed through the ordinary trial and that the claim be adapted, so that in 2018 the community filed the claim again including, this time, the collective map made together with the anthropologist Lorena Cardin. In 2021 the SCJN rejected the exceptions presented by the other parties (province of Formosa and the National Parks Administration) and ordered to transfer again; the community had to re-file its lawsuit. To this day, end of 2024, the community is still waiting for the judicial sentence to be issued.

Qarashe (leader) Félix Díaz during a participatory mapping activity. Photograph by Lorena Cardin, 2013.

Case 6

Development policies in the Reserva Grande in Chaco, northeastern Argentina¹⁴

Keywords

Development policies

Land titling

El impenetrable Chaco

Socio-spatial transformations

Type of accumulation

Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

La Reserva Grande is located in the Chaco Impenetrable, a forested area that forms part of the Gran Chaco region, the second largest forest in Latin America, stretching across Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil and Paraguay. Here we can see the consequences of land grabbing, rights abuses and various extractive practices with serious impacts on the Global South, including deforestation for soy and cattle ranching. The Gran Chaco is one of the forests with the highest rate of deforestation in the world (Bossio et al., 2021; Paolasso et al., 2012), which has had a negative impact on the quality of life of the communities living in the area, particularly in terms of increased hunger and poverty.

In this area, various actors are involved in ongoing conflicts over land. The cultural and ethnic diversity present is a complex factor when it comes to prioritising social problems and proposing public policies. Successive governments in the Chaco province have implemented policies for the titling of public land in favour of the indigenous *Wichi*, *Qom* and *Moqoit* communities, but the presence of the Creole population – who are not included in these policies – has led to tensions and territorial claims.

Between 2010 and 2023, two development models can be identified in the region: one that seeks to consolidate an exclusive territory for indigenous groups, and another that proposes a shared territoriality between indigenous and Creole populations. These models have been proposed through projects that articulate networks of multiple actors: public, private, local, national and others. Although successive provincial governments have tried to present development policies as neutral and rational, an analysis of these policies reveals their subjective character and their malleability to the economic interests present in the area.

Territorial accumulation can be understood in terms of the different dimensions present in the history of the Gran Chaco: the appropriation of the cheap labour of the Creole and indigenous populations, the regulation and control of these populations, the modification of their ways of life and the projects that have sought to impose certain visions of development on them; and the dispossession of their natural resources, mainly land and forests, which have historically been used according to the different productive and economic models that prevailed at the time (the timber and tanning industries, cotton and soya).

Territory

At present, disputes over belonging and permanence in the Gran Chaco are taking place in an economic context characterised by the exploitation of primary resources. As a result, the type of territorial accumulation that can be observed there is based on various neo-extractivist processes of land grabbing and exploitation of timber forests.

Although timber has historically been an exploitable commodity in the Chaco, with the expansion of the agricultural frontier in Argentina for the sowing of genetically modified soya (which, thanks to new technological models, can be sown in areas with scarce water resources) and the raising of livestock for export meat, fiscal lands have begun to be revalued.

[14] This review is based on research carried out by Jimena Ramos Berrondo and Matías Berger of the Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales (CEUR) at the University of Buenos Aires, Argentina.

These practices have led to socio-spatial transformations in the province of Chaco, with negative consequences for the population. On the other hand, the policies associated with the creation of nature reserves and land titling in favour of the indigenous and peasant population, although contradictory to the economic exploitation of the territory, can also be understood as a mechanism to mitigate the social, economic and environmental consequences caused by extractivism based on natural resources and dispossession through appropriation.

The research used a qualitative methodological strategy based on a case study, triangulating different collection methods: in-depth interviews, documentary analysis and participant observation. The focus was on recovering the voice of the actors, their culture and their perspectives, linked to historical constructions and to the struggles and resistances they have experienced and developed in order to denounce, make visible and confront the various forms of exploitation to which they are subjected: slave labour, dispossession of land, plundering of their natural resources, among others.

Wichi indigenous leaders in the 20,000 community hectares, in the Reserva Grande, Chaco province, Argentina.

The empirical work was carried out in two periods. The first, between 2010 and 2016, consisted of the geographical and demographic characterisation of the area, the identification of the influence of mediators and organisations, and the collection of testimonies from different actors about their work and the projects developed there (around 15 interviews with indigenous and creole leaders and state agents in the Chaco in 2009 and 2010); tours and participant observation in Teuco Bermejito with criollo and indigenous organisations (2009-2010); workshop with provincial officials at the Chaco School of Government (2012); tours and participant observation with the National Peasant Front (2015-2016).

Gathering of Creole farmers in the Reserva Grande, Chaco province, Argentina.

A second period of research will take place between 2021 and 2024. During the Covid-19 pandemic phase, interviews with criollo leaders were conducted remotely, and documentary analysis of decrees and laws of the province of Chaco related to public lands and natural resources, as well as analysis of historical documents, were carried out. With the possibility of face-to-face interviews and fieldwork, in-depth interviews were conducted between 2023 and 2024 with staff from the Colonisation Institute (the provincial government agency responsible for managing public lands), indigenous leaders, criollo leaders and government technicians in the field of family farming. We also analysed the various projects developed in the Reserva Grande and the studies carried out in the region (by the Colonisation Institute, the Inter-American Development Bank and others). Finally, with the support of the Chaco School of Government, a workshop was held with around 30 participants: Creole leaders, indigenous leaders from the Qom ethnic group, members of the Wichi ethnic group, an indigenous deputy from the Qom ethnic group, a deputy from the Frente de Izquierda, staff from the Committee against Torture, researchers from the Universidad Nacional del Nordeste (National University of the Northeast), lawyers from the Office of the General Counsel of the Government and staff from the Colonisation Institute.

Participating node

- Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales del Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CEUR-CONICET), Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina

Further information

- Ramos Berrondo, Jimena; Berger, Matías. “¿Cómo modelan las políticas de desarrollo los territorios en diferentes escalas? Un caso de estudio en la Reserva Grande en Chaco, Noreste de Argentina” (forthcoming).

Case 7

Infrastructures and logics of hydrological dispossession in the Katari Basin, Bolivia¹⁵

Keywords

Water pollution

Socio-ecological inequalities

Metabolism

Hydrological dispossession

Type of accumulation

Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources

Urbanisation, redevelopment, large projects and infrastructures

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The Katari Basin, in the department of La Paz, Bolivia, with an extension of almost 3,000 km², covers at least 9 urban and rural municipalities and is the most populated in the country. It is also the most emblematic basin in the Andean region due to its relationship with Lake Titicaca, a cultural reference point and a source of agricultural and livestock production of great importance for the food security of the metropolitan area.

In the first half of the 20th century, the current municipality of El Alto clearly demonstrated its operational-functional role in relation to the needs of the city of La Paz. It housed the workshops of the Bolivian Railway, the airport, the storage of hydrocarbons and the infrastructure for the supply of drinking water to the capital. In the second half of the 20th century, El Alto experienced explosive urban growth that far outstripped the state's capacity to provide essential services, leading to the current context of profound environmental degradation of this territory, in which a variety of complex interactions occur between agricultural and livestock communities, urbanising communities, resource extraction systems and public-private infrastructures.

In fact, the infrastructures have been part of the great system of resource extraction since the beginning of the 20th century. At the head of the Katari Basin, in the extreme north of El Alto, is the indigenous community of Alto Milluni, an area where the Milluni and Huayna Potosí mines began operating at the beginning of the 20th century, leading to the urbanisation of El Alto in a logic of peripheral urbanisation. In this community, camelid breeding has had to adapt to the contamination and diminution of its water sources and streams as a result of mining activities and the extraction and transfer of water sources by the Water and Sewerage Company for the benefit of the cities of La Paz and El Alto. Acid mine drainage, caused by decades of unmanaged environmental liabilities, makes it impossible to use the water for agriculture, let alone livestock. More recently, attacks by feral dogs from the outskirts of El Alto have discouraged livestock farming. The community is currently in conflict with a mining company that collects mining waste and tailings to be processed in Viacha – a municipality located downstream – and dumped into the

rivers that flow into Lake Titicaca. The impact of climate change on the shrinking glaciers in this part of the Andes is putting further pressure on scarce water resources.

In the extreme south of El Alto, the Marka Indígena Originaria Aymara de Puchukollo, located in the municipality of Laja, is a degraded territory torn between integration into the urban sprawl of El Alto and the state of rural periphery in its own municipality. Every day, dozens of trucks loaded with construction waste are dumped directly into the Seco River, one of the main rivers in this basin, the most polluted and the main source of water for irrigation in the area. To the south-east, the sewage treatment plant emits a strong odour of phosphorous and discharges dark water both into the outfall and into the treated water channel. At the other end, to the west, are the extensive wetlands and cultivated areas that the Puchukollo Alto community is trying to protect from urban sprawl. Near this wetland, the water company has constructed a series of 36 wells that draw water from the aquifer to supply the southern part of El Alto.

[15] This review is based on research by Carlos Revilla of Universidad Mayor de San Andrés (UMSA) and the Instituto de Investigación y Acción para el Desarrollo Integral (IIADI) in Bolivia.

Milluni Lagoon (Colorado) contaminated with iron and acid drainage from mining activities in Alto Milluni, upper basin. Photograph by IIADI, 2019.

The areas described, Alto Milluni and Alto Puchukollo, in the extreme north and south of El Alto, are thus an example of the transformation of the landscape and of social relations in the urban-rural boundary, caused by the pressure on resources and aggravated by the effects of climate change, but above all by the determining role played by infrastructure both in the processes of dispossession and territorial accumulation and in the unequal metabolic exchange between different spaces and territories, especially between urban and rural space; an unequal exchange that is constitutive of the socio-ecological injustices resulting from the extraction of energy and materials. Neo-extractivism leads to the dispossession of indigenous lands and ways of life, mainly through water pollution.

Hydrological dispossession, which causes metabolic imbalances in the area, occurs in many different ways: directly through water extraction infrastructures; through a model of water resource appropriation that involves the permanent drilling of wells; because the recharge zones

of aquifers and wetlands become impermeable due to the growth of urban sprawl; through the pollution generated by the inadequate sewage treatment system; through the application of hydraulic technologies such as the overlapping of basins, the redirection of water flows, and others. All these modalities have as a condition the control of the territory, they establish power relations with the actors of the intervened spaces, either because the control of the water is taken away from them or because they are excluded from its access (Perales, 2022). The water balance of the basin is broken, disrupting natural cycles and the community dynamics of water decision-making and management. In turn, deficiencies in the management of wastewater collection and treatment infrastructures lead to metabolic imbalances with both environmental and social consequences in the peripheral and rural areas of the lower basin. The monopolistic nature of both private and public water and sanitation companies makes it difficult to implement government regulation and social control mechanisms.

Action research in the upper and lower basin

The perspective of extensive urbanisation recognises that urbanisation processes are not confined to urban spaces, but that their impacts extend beyond urban boundaries when they affect, for example, water resources and rural spaces. The research reviewed here seeks to analyse the transformation of the landscape and social relations in the communities that form part of the Katari Basin, particularly those located on the urban-rural border.

From the action research approach, different interventions have been carried out in this territory to respond to their needs, to understand the socio-territorial dynamics and to produce useful, applicable and appropriable knowledge. The approach is based on the management of the basin as a concept and as a spatiality, in such a way that the accompaniment of the communities includes both the upper and the lower basin, articulated by their own socio-environmental relations.

Truck unloading construction waste on the Seco River in the Alto Puchukollo community. Photograph by IIADI, 2022.

The research action carried out aims to develop processes of reflection with local actors on the impact of extractive infrastructures on urbanisation, to identify and name the socio-territorial inequalities they generate, and to make visible and appropriate territorial contestation.

In the upper basin, Alto Milluni, interventions are focused on supporting the development of a community tourism project that the community has undertaken in recent years. The action supports the management and implementation of tourism services such as the "Suma phukhu Milluni" gastronomic centre, run by 36 women, and the "Miner for a day" activity, run by 20 former mine workers and members of the community.

In the lower basin, pollution caused by the discharge of solid and liquid waste into the rivers brings chemical, biological and pathological pollutants. The need and demand of the communities is to decontaminate the water of their rivers, for which a double pilot project has been designed and implemented, consisting of a system of retention and extraction of solid waste from the Seco and Pallina rivers, known as Biobarda (with the participation of the Instituto de Investigaciones Mecánicas y Electromecánicas of the Universidad Mayor de San Andrés, Bolivia) and the application of a water

decontamination technology using biochar (with the participation of the University of Newcastle, UK), both of which were implemented in the community of Machacamarca Baja.

The aim was to contribute to the immediate exercise of the fundamental rights to water, healthy food and health in communities affected by pollution and, from a broader perspective, to the right to a healthy, protected and balanced environment. And, through the action itself, to raise environmental awareness in the communities concerned. In addition to reflection, the mitigation of the problem was made possible by the alliance and joint efforts of academia and local communities.

Alto Milluni water transfer channel to the city of La Paz. Photograph by IIADI, 2019.

Participating nodes

- Universidad Mayor de San Andrés (UMSA), Bolivia
- Instituto de Investigación y Acción para el Desarrollo Integral (IIADI), Bolivia

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<https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/bolivia/>

Case 8

Infrastructure provision as a mechanism of territorial accumulation¹⁶

Keywords

Rent extraction

Copper mining

Economic development

Luksic Group

Type of accumulation

Urbanisation, redevelopment, large projects and infrastructures

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

In the 21st century, infrastructure provision has become an important mechanism of territorial accumulation (Castro *et al.*, 2022 in Kanai and Telles, 2023). The discourse of the infrastructure deficit as an obstacle to economic growth has become pervasive and influential in Latin America, leading states to mobilise to address 'infrastructure gaps' (Lin, 2022; Hope, 2022 in Kanai and Telles, 2023) by promoting, through new or restructured state agencies, the construction of infrastructure projects of varying scale with the support of foreign investment. Infrastructure development is a component of both bilateral and multilateral free trade and cooperation agreements, and national governments have extended their planning to previously unconnected or 'backward' territories now considered valuable to extractivist networks (Kanai and Schindler, 2019).

The hegemonic economic model considers infrastructure investments essential for economic development, positive for territorial connectivity and useful for certain economic, social and environmental objectives, but critical studies show their high negative impacts at the socio-environmental level, such as the development of extensive urbanisation in peri-urban spaces characterised by multiple precariousness; deforestation and pollution with serious social and environmental consequences, and consequent conflict in the territories.

Using critical analysis as the main tool, based on literature review and case studies, the political-economic dimension of territorial accumulation is analysed, with an emphasis

on describing how capital accumulation works through the extraction of rents through infrastructure, specifically the functioning of the vertical integration of infrastructural circuits.

Alongside state action, large private corporations are a key-actor in infrastructure-driven development. They operationalise and strategically link rural and urban spaces through a variety of material and socio-political infrastructure types, monopolising the various components of the extractive industry.

This is the case of copper mining in Chile. The Luksic Group is a paradigmatic example, whose activities have diversified and expanded in recent years to include the mining, transport, loading and shipping of ore from the Andes to the Atacama Desert, through the urban fabric of Antofagasta and the Pacific Ocean to ports in North America and China, where the minerals are unloaded (Lukas, 2022).

This logistics chain begins at the copper and gold mines 180 kilometres from Antofagasta; Antofagasta Minerals, Chile's largest private mining company, extracts the minerals, which are then transported by pipeline, road and rail. The Antofagasta Bolivia Railway, founded in 1888 during the saltpetre era, has been owned by the Luksic Group since 1980; its network of more than 900 kilometres is dedicated exclusively to the transport of mining inputs and products.

Territories

[16] This review is based on research by Miguel Kanai of the University of Sheffield, UK, and Michael Lukas of the University of Chile.

The main destination for the minerals is the port terminal ATI (Antofagasta Terminal Internacional), which is controlled by Luksic and exclusively serves the mining industry. The minerals are first stored at ATI and then loaded onto large container ships operated by Compañía Sudamericana de Vapores (CSAV), which the Luksic group has also controlled since 2011. In 2014, it also acquired the German shipping company Hapag-Lloyd, which is the fourth largest container shipping company in the world with a fleet of 200 ships. Between 2003 and 2015, Luksic also controlled Aguas Antofagasta, the city's main water company.

Port of Mejillones, Antofagasta region. Photograph by Dorothea Wolf, 2024.

Logistics chain of mineral extraction

Source: Lukas, 2022.

Participating nodes

- University of Sheffield, United Kingdom
- Universidad de Chile, Chile

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Case 9

Extractivism, infrastructure and urbanisation: the extractive circuit in Antofagasta, Chile¹⁷

Keywords

Global networks

Mining extractivism

Extractive urbanisation

Logistics

Type of accumulation

Urbanisation, redevelopment, large projects and infrastructures

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

As the region with the largest saltpetre and copper reserves, Antofagasta is a city historically linked to mining. The saltpetre industry was the main economic activity in Chile between 1880 and 1930, and copper in the first three decades of the 20th century. Throughout the 20th century, the country's extractivist model underwent important changes, with the colonial extractivism of saltpetre diversifying into a matrix of extraction and export of natural resources that now includes salmon, wood products and fruit as its main products, in addition to copper.

With the state already playing a strong role in the economy, the military dictatorship (1973-1989) deepened extractive activities by implementing structural reforms that facilitated the arrival of foreign capital and the privatisation of the sector. More recently, however, many of the mining (copper, but also lithium, gold and silver) and hydroelectric projects have met with very strong resistance from citizens and environmental organisations, reflecting a new cycle of territorial mobilisations and the exhaustion of the neoliberal consensus in Chile. In 2012 and 2013, following the expansion of the port in the centre of the city of Antofagasta, open conflicts erupted in the face of pollution problems caused by various territorial projects, mainly mining. Citizens mobilised under the slogan "This dust is killing you".

In response, the state created a more complex environmental structure (Environmental Courts, Environmental Superintendence, Environmental Assessment Service and Ministry of the Environment) and proposed some reforms, mainly in the mining, forestry and fishing sectors; it also recognised the problem of "sacrifice zones", towns with a high concentration of polluting activities, and created Environmental and Social Recovery Plans.

For its part, the response of the business world, in order to create a new basis of legitimacy, was to adapt its classic model of corporate social responsibility to a more complex scheme of citizen participation and urban and territorial governance. In 2013, in order to appease social protest against urban insecurity and mining pollution, BHP Billiton launched a strategic urban planning initiative, the CREO Antofagasta programme, co-opting the mobilised groups but also demonstrating the emerging links between transnational resource extraction circuits and global urbanism (Lukas, 2022).

Antofagasta: logistical hub of transnational mining and epicentre of popular urbanisation

Through a large logistical system that responds to national and transnational production networks in the extractive industries – such as Chile's state-owned CODELCO, Chile's Luksic Group and South Africa's BHP Billiton, the world's largest private mining company – the "extraction circuit" articulates the mining deposits located 180 km from the city with various means of transporting the mined ore (trucks, rail systems and pipelines) that take the minerals to port facilities for transport by shipping companies to external, mainly Asian, markets. Indeed, the national urban system in Chile is characterised by the interconnectedness between the hinterland and the operational landscapes of resource extraction.

[17] This review is based on research by Michael Lukas of the University of Chile.

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Railway track and FCAB (railway company) locomotive with the city of Antofagasta in the background. Photograph by Claudia Alonso, 2024.

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Despite the large amounts of capital involved in all this transnational logistics, local economic development is incipient and the city of Antofagasta is very poor. The extractive regions and their cities are merely logistical functions for the benefit of global production networks. Thus, in the last decade there has been a real estate boom linked to the logistical urbanisation of extractivism (and speculative urbanisation) and, in parallel, an exponential growth of popular urbanisation through land grabs and encampments: between 2011 and 2016, encampments on the urban periphery increased by more than 480%, and around 5,000 families live in more than 500 land occupations with self-built homes.

Extractive urbanisation

The review and analysis of secondary sources, network analysis, observation and field visits, as well as the collection of almost 50 interviews, allowed us to examine the ways in which large national and international economic groups seek to intervene in the planning and urban governance of the extractive city. The research carried out makes it possible to establish the concept of extractive urbanisation (EU) from a geo-historical perspective, which is absent in Latin American and international urban theory.

Extractive urbanisation is characterised by long-lasting infrastructural and metabolic configurations that are subject to abrupt changes in relation to the cycles of international commodity markets, namely extractive urbanisation produces urban processes with a specific temporality, spatiality and political dynamics.

It is also possible to draw some theoretical lessons for urban-territorial studies of the processes of territorial accumulation through mining extractivism. The study of the relationship between extractivism, infrastructure and urbanisation requires a broadening of the concept of extractivism, taking into account both its classical meaning, associated with the exploitation of raw materials, and the meaning it acquires in urban contexts, referring to the intensive exploitation of certain land uses, generating processes of dispossession, accumulation and rent extraction. On the other hand, it highlights the need to understand the role of elites and local and transnational companies in the orchestration of territorial projects at different scales, including the logistical chains of extractive networks (in this case, the Luksic Group and BHP Billiton), which combine and functionally integrate mining deposits, transport infrastructure, desalination plants, urban spaces, ports and planning instruments (Lukas *et al.*, n.d.).

Extractivist infrastructure in Mejillones, a mining town on the coast. Photograph by Michael Lukas, 2024.

Participating node

- Universidad de Chile, Chile

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Case 10

Networks of peri-urban extractivism in Colina, Metropolitan Region of Santiago, Chile¹⁸

Keywords

- Peri-urban extractivism
- Land conflicts
- Mining
- Natural assets
- Logistics
- Real estate projects

Type of accumulation

- Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources
- Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds, tourism, gentrification

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The municipality of Colina, located in the north of the metropolitan region of Santiago, is one of the most demographically dynamic areas in Chile. The explanation for this intense growth is linked to a public-private strategy of promoting human settlements on the outskirts of the metropolitan area through "conditional planning", which began in 1997 and left the definition of urban and residential development of tens of thousands of hectares in the rural area of Colina in private hands.

In the 2000s, several real estate megaprojects were developed that were a success for the upper-middle and upper-class housing market. They are characterised by gated communities with evergreen landscapes, connected by private highways to the eastern and wealthy sector of the Santiago Metropolitan Area (Área Metropolitana de Santiago), and some even have amenities such as artificial lagoons several hectares in size.

The other side of Colina's urban reality, however, is the significant increase in migrant camps along the Colina River. A peculiar structure, known locally as the "wall of shame", serves as a division between the new camps and the gated condominiums; a material and symbolic expression of the exclusionary rationality of the political economy of real estate development in the sector.

The infrastructures of peri-urban extractivism have multi-scale interactions and diffuse boundaries, showing the complexity of their material and immaterial consequences in the production of contested territories on the outskirts of large Latin American cities such as Santiago. Transformations and territorial conflicts that involve not only urban extractivism, but also historical mining extractivism.

This process of urban development and intense territorial transformations took place at the same time as Colina positioned itself as one of the most important mining territories in the country. The 'Los Bronces' mine is one of the world's largest copper producers, and since the late 1990s it has intensified its production, whose waste ends up in a dump a few kilometres from the main urban centre of Colina.

To legitimise their presence, the companies that own the mine – Anglo American, Codelco-Mitsui and Mitsubishi Corp – have adopted various community engagement strategies as part of their corporate responsibility policies, donating public infrastructure such as parks and plazas and providing water management technology to rural communities. However, local communities are resisting further expansion projects by the mining company.

[18] This review is based on research by Michael Lukas of the University of Chile.

Los Bronces mine pipeline, located in the Andes Mountains, crosses over the Colina River and extends for dozens of kilometers. It feeds a mining tailings deposit near the city of Colina, a site of contention between local communities and extractivist agents. Photograph by Ignacio Arce, 2024.

These territorial conflicts have led to the emergence of local groups whose members recognise that they are exposed to forms of material and symbolic violence emanating from the infrastructure of peri-urban extractivism, to which they respond by territorially contesting the protection of the Colina River and its surroundings.

This research uses territorial accumulation as a theoretical concept to understand the logics of infrastructure production in the context of peri-urban extractivism, and to capture the different edges and boundaries of the nexus between natural resource extractivism and urban extractivism.

The empirical work was carried out between 2023 and 2024. Field observation, mapping of peri-urban extractivist infrastructures, 'walking interviews' with members of social organisations and press reviews form the main structure of its methodological strategy.

The results made it possible to map the infrastructural network of peri-urban extractivism in an inter-communal, inter-regional and international sense and to propose typologies of infrastructures of mining and real estate territories.

Participating node

- Universidad de Chile, Chile

Further information

- "Redes del extractivismo periurbano en Colina", in the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation. <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/colina/>

Case 11

The tenant odyssey¹⁹

Keywords

Rental housing

Real estate market

Tenant survey

Tenancy

Type of accumulation

Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The rental housing market has received increasing attention in housing debates as a result of the intense processes of commodification and tenantisation that position housing as a key aspect of global cycles of capital accumulation. Since the collapse of the global real estate and financial markets in 2007, there has been a dramatic global trend towards increasing numbers of renter households, even in societies that have historically been characterised as landlord societies, thereby deepening the social divide between tenants and landlords (IDRA, 2023). This suggests that the expansion of the rental market is caused by the combination of the direct consequences of the crisis for the majority of the population: precarious wages, limited borrowing capacity, the impossibility of owning a home, the lack of social housing programmes and the deregulation of housing legislation and public policies.

In this way, rented housing is positioned as one of the solutions (fixes) to the crisis caused mainly by the speculative production of housing as a commodity. In recent decades, rental housing has played a fundamental role in the reinvention of capital in the face of crises of accumulation, initiating cycles of private property concentration and rent extraction. The expansion of the mercantile frontier towards the intensive and continuous extraction of rent from rented housing opens a cycle of profit generation that subordinates to capitalist accumulation the uses, needs and relations that revolve around housing and its relation to the reproduction of human life. This process has territorial and socio-habitat effects that, on the one hand, aggravate the housing crisis and unequal urban development since the 2007 crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic, and, on the other hand, shape new types of contestation and struggles over the right to habitability and the city.

Territories

The rental market appears as a relevant problem for urban research because it allows us to study property speculation and its effects, such as gentrification, as well as the specific dynamics of dispossession, displacement and exclusion that these processes generate on a global scale. This kind of research implies the adoption of theoretical approaches that integrate complex interpretations of neoliberal urban models based on land appropriation, real estate rent extraction and the capitalisation of the precariousness of urban populations' ways of life. Urban extractivism, understood as a modality of territorial accumulation, is one of the most important interpretative approaches for the simultaneous study of the territorial logics of capital and its effects on the population. This concept is influenced by the theoretical keys developed in the Latin American context around the notion of extractivism, which critically examine the networks and productive circuits of capital beyond its economic dimension, that is, by examining its environmental, cultural and social dimensions.

[19] This overview was prepared on the basis of the research reports of the nodes participating in this survey.

However, the lack of quantitative data for the analysis of urban extractivism has been an obstacle to understanding the dynamics of rental markets, despite their influence on the material and symbolic reality of a large percentage of tenant households worldwide. In particular, this has made it difficult to consider fundamental aspects of these markets, such as:

- 1 The practices and interests of large landlords, including real estate agencies and construction companies
- 2 Access to housing
- 3 Impacts on housing habitability conditions
- 4 Characteristics of tenancy relationships
- 5 Residential mobility (visible and invisible moves or evictions)

The lack of quantitative data highlights the need to develop methodological tools that contribute to research on the impact of tenancy processes in different cities around the world. The "Survey on the Social Impacts of the Rental Market", also known as the "Tenants' Survey", appears to be a response to this need, as it provides statistically reliable inputs with the aim of producing city-by-city diagnoses and comparative studies between the cities in which it has been carried out. In this way, this research method can be replicated in heterogeneous urban contexts, taking into account their similarities and, at the same time, their specificities. At present, the tenant survey has been carried out in both Latin American and European cities: Barcelona and Madrid (Spain), Lisbon (Portugal), Buenos Aires (Argentina), Leipzig and Karlsruhe (Germany), and will be extended to Manchester (UK) and Santiago de Chile (Chile).

% of tenants in the cities	
Barcelona	40%
Madrid	26%
Buenos Aires	34%
Lisbon	29%
Leipzig	84%
Karlsruhe	36%

Barcelona and Madrid

The tenant survey was designed by IDRA (Institut de Recerca Urbana de Barcelona) in collaboration with local organisations, mainly the Observatori Metropolità de l'Habitatge and Sindicat de Llogateres, which aim to improve the conditions of habitability and guarantee access to housing in Barcelona. The survey started in Barcelona in 2018. Between October and December 2022, 1,023 non-probabilistic surveys were carried out through quotas of residents over 16 years old, tenants and informed about the main economic decisions of their household (IDRA, 2023). The survey was conducted in two ways: online, using the NetQuest tool, and face-to-face, by IDRA researchers.

The combined analysis of the data collected through the survey and the interviews revealed two main trends.

Pollster in a housing complex in the Vallecas district of Madrid. Photograph by the polling team, 2023.

Firstly, the increasing management of the rental housing supply by real estate agencies (74.8% of rentals) and, as a consequence, the professionalisation of the rental market, especially among large landlords with more than 10 properties (80.5% of large landlords use real estate agencies). Secondly, and as a consequence of the first, the deterioration of access to housing and rental conditions for tenants; the management of rents by real estate agencies tends to increase (i) discrimination on the basis of employment and ethnicity, (ii) dissatisfaction with housing, (iii) problems between landlords and tenants, (iv) rental prices and (v) intention to move (IDRA, 2024).

In Madrid, 1,170 non-probabilistic quota-based surveys were carried out between October and December 2023 among tenants aged 16 and over who were informed about household economic decisions.

[20] The non-probabilistic quota survey is a data collection instrument that allows for the selection of a representative sample of the population. The feature to determine this sample depends on the researcher's knowledge and relationship with the context where the survey will be applied.

The design of the survey was based on the guidelines of the survey used in Barcelona, but adapted to the conditions of the city following the contributions of the Madrid Tenants' Association. The survey was also carried out in two ways: online, using the NetQuest tool, and face-to-face, by researchers from IDRA, Basurama and ACIJ.

The analysis of the data collected and its comparison with the Barcelona survey shows that the incidence of rental housing management by estate agents has increased over the last 5 years in Madrid (34.1% of rentals), although the degree of penetration of estate agents in the rental market is less pronounced than in Barcelona. Although the direct relationship between *lx arrendatarix* and *lx inquilinx* is still predominant, it is declining when considering contracts of less than one year (41.7% signed with estate agents) (IDRA, 2024). Similarly to Barcelona, the greater presence of real estate agencies in the management of rented housing in Madrid has led to more obstacles to access to housing and a deterioration in living conditions for tenants, who experience discrimination in access to housing (35% of tenants), higher real estate fees (64.2% of tenants with less than 5 years) and dissatisfaction with housing conditions (63% of tenants) (IDRA, 2024).

The increase in rental housing managed by real estate agencies is linked to the deregulation of real estate intermediation in Spain, despite regulatory efforts to decentralise its influence on the rental market. The analysis of the data collected allowed us to formulate a series of public policy recommendations aimed at the different dimensions of the real estate market: (i) that the competent authorities develop a binding model contract, (ii) establish mechanisms to share tenants' experiences, (iii) decouple fees from the amount of rent, (iv) develop a system of inspection and sanction of bad rental practices, (v) disseminate the rights and responsibilities of actors within a rental relationship.

Press conference for the presentation of the report on rental conditions in Barcelona. Photograph by IDRA, 2023.

In May 2002, the same month that the Law on the Right to Housing was adopted in Spain, the preliminary results of the survey were disseminated, helping to reduce uninformed prejudices about the problem of tenancy and to qualify the debate on the new legislation.

Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area

In Argentina, after the 2001 crisis, the expansion of real estate activity had an impact on land and real estate prices, which, particularly in the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area, increased at different rates and over different periods of time, far exceeding the relative prices of other goods and services. This, added to the dollarization of the real estate market and the lack of access to mortgage credit, led to the sustained growth of the tenant population (tenantization), which has also found it increasingly difficult to access rental housing. The tenant survey implemented in the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area is aimed precisely at producing information about tenant households.

In November 2022, 1,508 telephone interviews were conducted using the IVR system with people aged 16 and over who were renters and who were informed about the main economic decisions of their households. At the same time, 445 non-probabilistic face-to-face surveys were carried out in instalments among tenants in poor neighbourhoods of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area and in boarding houses and tenements in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (ACBA). The sample was selected according to the different types of housing in the AMBA areas, both in the working-class neighbourhoods – villas and settlements – and in the central neighbourhoods of Buenos Aires.

The fieldwork was carried out through alliances with social organisations. In the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area's popular neighbourhoods, we worked with the Frente de Organizaciones en Lucha (FOL), the Frente Arde Rojo (FAR), Hábitat Sur, the Corriente Villera Independiente, the Centro para una Justicia Igualitaria y Popular (CEJIP) and neighbourhood representatives from Barrio 31. The interviews were conducted by representatives of the area, neighbours from the neighbourhoods themselves and researchers from the UBA, ACIJ and CEUR-CONICET. The surveys in the rooming houses and tenements were carried out between December 2022 and March 2023, in coordination with "La Boca Resiste y Propone" and "Consejerías de Vivienda", organisations that have accompanied processes of resistance against evictions in different neighbourhoods of ACBA.

Amancay neighborhood, Northern Zone of the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires. Renting in popular neighborhoods, a modality of access to housing that is gaining relevance in recent years. Photograph by Ricardo Apaolaza, 2022.

The survey examined the situation of tenant households in the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area from three dimensions: (i) economic and financial situation, (ii) housing conditions, and (iii) challenges in accessing the rental market. Analysis of the data revealed persistent precariousness, housing instability and vulnerability among renter households, exacerbated among female-headed households (ACIJ et al., 2023; ACIJ et al., 2024). The data showed that 63% of households have moved home in the last 5 years; 63% of renter households are in debt and 62% out of this 63% allocated the debt amounts to rent payments; more than 50% of renter households are overcrowded and 33% out of this 50% report critical overcrowding (more than 3 people per room) (ACIJ et al., 2023). In terms of gender and care, 40% of renter households with children and/or people with disabilities experience barriers to accessing housing.

Hotel Residencial located in the neighborhood named Constitución, one of the oldest neighborhoods in the City of Buenos Aires. Renting rooms in hotels is a historical strategy used by popular sectors to access the urban center. Photography by Agustín Nizzoli, 2023.

Between August and October 2023, in the absence of official figures, the data produced by the survey was central to the public debate on the Rent Act. Debates were held in the national parliament, in which researchers involved in the implementation of the survey participated with presentations on the functioning of rents in Argentina, to demonstrate the need for a rent control policy. The media – both conventional and unconventional – used the data from the survey as a strategy to promote public debate on the real estate market and the heterogeneity of tenant structures.

Lisbon Metropolitan Area

During 2023, the Habita65 organisation carried out the tenant survey in Lisbon, Portugal. The first two phases of the analysis of the data collected were carried out in collaboration with IDRA, the Observatorio de l'habitatge de Barcelona and the Centro de Estudos Sociais de Coimbra. Between February and April 2023, 882 non-probabilistic quota surveys were carried out among Lisbon residents aged 18 and over, who were tenants and informed about the main economic decisions of their household. The survey was conducted in two ways: online surveys using the NetQuest tool (68.61%) and face-to-face and telephone surveys (31.39%).

The face-to-face and telephone surveys were carried out by Habita65 researchers in partnership with the Lisbonenses Tenants Association, the Immigrant Solidarity Association and the Olho Vivo Association. The purpose of using this survey method was to overcome the limitations of online surveys, namely the under-representation of the most vulnerable tenant population, with lower digital literacy and socio-economic resources.

The aim of this survey was to build up a picture of this tenure system from the characteristics of tenancy contracts and rented dwellings, as well as of the resident population in the different tenancy situations. It was possible to identify the existence of a tripartite rental market, composed of three market segments – liberalised, protected and informal – that provide different frameworks for the contractual relationship between landlords and tenants, associated with different housing conditions and socio-demographic characteristics. The liberalised market segment is the largest and targets the working-age population, which is heavily burdened by housing costs due to the high rents of the most recent and short-term rental contracts; it is a market that generates a high level of contractual instability by not guaranteeing the renewal of contracts and where rents are freely updated between contracts. The protected market is made up of pre-1990 contracts, which cover an

older population and offer a higher level of contractual regulation and lower rents, but this market is made up of dwellings in the worst possible condition, often in poor condition. As tenants cannot afford to move to the liberalised market, they are forced to remain in very unsatisfactory housing. Finally, the informal market, although a smaller but growing segment, has the worst housing conditions and targets a vulnerable population.

The analysis of the data showed that housing is not only an increasingly important factor in reproducing and reinforcing social inequalities and patterns of residential segregation, including the determinants of social class, occupation, age, gender, nationality and ethnicity, but also has an increasingly direct impact on the mental health of the tenant population. Indeed, housing conditions are an important factor in the development of anxiety due to the high level of insecurity associated with remaining in the dwelling and the lack of alternatives, or even violence through harassment practices aimed at forcing people to leave the property of their own volition. The high level of mobility observed in the constant change of housing in a few years for part of the tenant population, a phenomenon called invisible evictions, is a sign of vulnerability and housing instability.

Knowledge of the living conditions in the different segments of the rental market, which are in a constant state of flux, is essential for the design of public housing policies that are able to address the specificities of the different realities of the rental market, as well as the perverse dynamics that reinforce each other and exacerbate the housing crisis in Portugal.

Tenants' march, the demand says: "For our lives, for our homes." Photograph by Habita65, 2022.

Participating nodes

- Institut de Recerca Urbana de Barcelona (IDRA), Spain
- Habita65 - Associação pelo direito à habitação e à cidade, Portugal
- Instituto de Geografía de la Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina
- Asociación Civil por la Igualdad y la Justicia (Civil Association for Equality and Justice), Argentina
- Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Argentina
- Basurama, Spain
- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain
- Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
- Leipzig University, Germany

Further information

- Institut de Recerca Urbana de Barcelona (IDRA) (2024). **Impacto de las inmobiliarias en el mercado del alquiler.** Estudio a partir de la encuesta realizada en Madrid y Barcelona. https://idrabcn.com/es/publicacion/informe_inmobiliarias/
- ACIJ; CELS; CEUR-CONICET; EIDAES; IGEO-UBA (2023). **Deuda, habitabilidad y alquiler. La situación de los hogares inquilinos en el AMBA.** <https://www.contested-territories.net/deuda-habitabilidad-y-alquiler/>
- ACIJ; CELS; CEUR-CONICET; EIDAES; IGEO-UBA (2024). **Encuesta Inquilina 2024: Alquilar en el AMBA en tiempos de libre mercado.** <https://www.cels.org.ar/web/publicaciones/encuesta-inquilina-2024-alquilar-en-amba-en-tiempos-de-libre-mercado/>
- ACIJ; CELS; CEUR-CONICET; EIDAES; IGEO-UBA (2023). **El alquiler de piezas en hoteles-pensión y conventillos en la Ciudad de Buenos Aires: Situación socio-económica y habitacional.** <https://www.cels.org.ar/web/publicaciones/el-alquiler-de-piezas-en-hoteles-pension-y-conventillos-en-la-ciudad-de-buenos-aires-situacion-socio-economica-y-habitacional/>
- ACIJ; CELS; CEUR-CONICET; EIDAES; IGEO-UBA (2023). **Alquilar en los barrios populares del Área Metropolitana de Buenos Aires: condiciones sociales, económicas y habitacionales.** <https://www.cels.org.ar/web/publicaciones/alquilar-en-los-barrios-populares-del-area-metropolitana-de-buenos-aires-condiciones-sociales-economicas-y-habitacionales/>

Demonstration in Lisbon for the right to housing; demands read: "Mass tourism is harmful", "Freeze rents, stop evictions". Photography by Habita65, 2022.

Case 12

Short-term rentals as new forms of territorial accumulation

*Airbnb in Buenos Aires City and Santiago de Chile*²¹

Keywords

Rental market

Short term rentals

Rental real estate

Airbnb

Type of accumulation

Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds, touristification

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The emergence of digital platforms, initially aimed at tourist accommodation, has boosted a sub-market of short-term rentals in an increasing number of cities. Santiago de Chile and the city of Buenos Aires are two Latin American contexts crossed by the process of tenantisation or the increase of rentals, where the territorial impact of the sub-market of short-term rentals is explored through the analysis of the Airbnb platform.

Indeed, the platforms facilitate the massive diffusion of supply and act as safe and convenient intermediaries for both buyers and sellers. However, the fundamental reason for this disruption of the property market is that they offer the owner an unprecedented flexibility in terms of contract conditions, price and duration of stay, which could make it possible to achieve extraordinary profitability compared to long-term rentals, due to the higher turnover of capital. In this way, the contradiction between the use value and the exchange value of housing is exacerbated by facilitating the increasing prioritisation of its function as a store of value or financial asset over its social value.

Territories

Territorial pattern of Airbnb supply in Buenos Aires City, Argentina. Source: Inside Airbnb, 2023.

In this way, digital platforms favour the dynamics of "territorial accumulation", understood as the way in which capital advances over people, territories and nature, accumulating through the appropriation of elements that are still outside the traditional circuits of global capital (Castro et al., 2022 in Lerena and Orozco, n.d.). Short-term rentals constitute forms of territorial accumulation in these Latin American cities in two ways. On the one hand, they stimulate the exit from the market of complete dwellings oriented towards the satisfaction of shelter needs, to be placed on the real estate market and deregulated global tourism; this drives the transnationalisation of local rents from the peripheries to the global north and concentrates accumulation in actors or platforms that are emerging or becoming more complex, such as digital platforms, developers, professionalised managers and real estate investors, while limiting access for tenant households. On the other hand, short-term rentals of rooms in one's own home represent an advance in the commodification of domestic space, which is still off-limits to capital.

[21] This review is based on research by Natalia Lerena Rongvaux of the Instituto de Geografía, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina; and Hernán Orozco of the Universidad Tecnológica Metropolitana, Chile.

The methodology used in this study is based on the development of indicators based on information from databases on the operation of the Airbnb platform in Latin America from two units of analysis: Santiago de Chile and the city of Buenos Aires, and a mixed comparative analysis of different dimensions.

The methodological approach of the research was mainly qualitative. Two main procedures were carried out: 1. The description of each of the cities was based on quantitative data and geo-referencing from the open platform Inside Airbnb, complemented in the Argentinean case by information on the long-term rental property market systematised by the General Directorate of Statistics and Census of the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, and in the Chilean case by information from the reports of the Rental Observatory of the Institute of Urban and Territorial Studies of the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile (IUTS-PUC); 2. A qualitative analysis based on the description made and on the systematisation of the specialised bibliography.

The comparative analysis has made it possible to integrate quantitative dimensions with a qualitative approach to the territorial dynamics of both cities, at the neighbourhood and metropolitan scale, and has identified three trends: (i) the expansion of the sub-market of short-term rentals of complete dwellings in consolidated and urban renewal areas, (ii) a significant presence of room rentals in private homes, in peripheral urban sectors and beyond tourist circuits, and (iii) the professionalisation of hosts and the emergence of new actors in the chain of urban rent extraction.

Territorial pattern of Airbnb supply in Santiago, Chile. Source: Inside Airbnb, 2023.

Participating node

- Instituto de Geografía de la Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina

Further information

- Lereña Rongvaux, Natalia; Orozco, Hernán. *“Alquileres a corto plazo como nuevas formas de acumulación territorial. Airbnb en Ciudad de Buenos Aires y Santiago de Chile”* (unpublished paper).

Case 13

Neoliberalism and the production of exclusionary cities: the sub-market of rented apartments in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires²²

Keywords

Rental under-market

Housing problems

Vulnerable households

Type of accumulation

Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The process of urban transformation based on the implementation of neoliberal policies, which began more than two decades ago in Argentina, has led to the intensification of real estate speculation and the exploitation of urban land in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires. This has led to serious difficulties in accessing formal housing and renting, especially for the most vulnerable sectors, who have been forced to seek housing alternatives in order to continue living in the city.

The Economic and Social Council of the City of Buenos Aires, in 2015 studies, stated that renter households living in the submarket of rented rooms (hotel-pension, tenement or conventillo) represent 10% of the city's renter population. This practice has historically been a housing option for low-income sectors that need urban centrality to access different urban goods (education, health, sources of employment, leisure, etc.) and that do not have the economic resources and requirements to access housing in the formal real estate market.

Territory

Family hotel located in the Constitución neighborhood, in the center of the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, which offers rooms for rent for housing. Photography by Agustín Nizzoli, 2023.

This form of access to housing, the rented housing sub-market, is characterised by poor living conditions: overcrowding, lack of infrastructure, fire hazards, risk of eviction, informality of contracts, etc., which are perpetuated by the lack of government control and the absence of public policies that regulate and/or respond to the housing problem in a sustainable manner. Although this market is growing, little is known about how it operates, how it is contracted and the conditions in which its inhabitants live.

Faced with this void, various institutions have joined forces in a collaborative manner to gather information through a survey that would make the problem of access to rental housing in the city of Buenos Aires more visible.

[22] This review is based on research carried out by María de la Paz Toscani and Paula Rosa of the Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales del Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CEUR-CONICET), Argentina.

From the primary information obtained by the Buenos Aires Tenants Survey, which conducted its data collection from December 2022 to March 2023, a selection of 110 surveys was made, selecting households that reside in the rental housing submarket on a long-term basis. These households are located in the following districts of ACBA: La Boca (30); Balvanera (22); Constitución (21), San Cristóbal (12), Monserrat (10), Almagro (4), San Telmo (3), Barracas (2), Boedo (2), Flores (1), Nueva Pompeya (1), Parque Patricios (1) and Villa Devoto (1).

The analysis of this information showed the inclusion of a sector of the impoverished middle class in the rented housing sub-market, affected by the elitisation of the rental market and its price increase, displacing to some extent the traditional low-income tenant sector. There has also been a deterioration in the building conditions of this type of housing and in the tenancy relationship established, which is characterised by insecurity of

tenure, housing instability, the possibility of eviction and the lack of a fixed tenancy period. On the other hand, a situation of indebtedness has been observed among tenant households, who have to take out loans to cover the cost of renting. Finally, although the conditions of access to these places are less restrictive, conditions such as the absence of minors were noted. Thus, the renting of rooms in hotels and apartment buildings adds a new dimension to the housing problem caused by the dynamics of urban extractivism in the city of Buenos Aires.

Participating node

- Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales del Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CEUR-CONICET), Argentina

Further information

- Toscani, María de la Paz; Rosa, Paula. [“Neoliberalismo y producción de ciudades excluyentes: el submercado de piezas en alquiler en la Ciudad de Buenos Aires”](#) (forthcoming).

Case 14

Mouraria, Lisbon: from tourist gentrification to articulating urban change²³

Keywords

Gentrification

Financialisation

Touristification

Type of accumulation

Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds, touristification, gentrification

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

Mouraria is a neighbourhood in the centre of Lisbon, historically characterised by its social diversity. Its spatial fabric is a maze of narrow streets on the slopes of two hills, with generous public spaces (Av. Almirante Reis and Martim Moniz Square) on its western edge. The neighbourhood has long been a border zone between the tourist districts of Baixa and Castelo and the residential districts of Anjos and Graça. Mouraria was one of the many neighbourhoods in southern European city centres where immigrant populations could find a 'back door to the city'; after decades of institutional disinvestment, coupled with discourses of its 'decadence', regeneration discourses and policies abound today.

The study of this historic Lisbon neighbourhood analyses the trajectory of the concept of gentrification, which is highly relevant within critical urban studies on a global scale. The authors argue that the extrapolation of a concept such as gentrification, originating in specific places and times, often leads to a loss of explanatory and strategic power. For this reason, they propose the concept of articulation developed by Laclau and Mouffe (in Tulumello and Allegretti, 2021), so that concepts such as gentrification, touristification and financialisation can 'travel' between places and levels of abstraction, increasing their analytical power.

In 2008, the municipal government made Mouraria the flagship of its regeneration strategy, through programmes that simplified the requirements for urban redevelopment and the sale of municipal housing in order to encourage private investment in real estate and construction. Between 2009 and 2011, in the context of the economic crisis in Portugal and the subsequent financial bailout with its associated austerity measures, the urban regeneration agenda – along with attracting tourism and international investment – became the centrepiece of the local anti-crisis strategy, in line with typical neoliberal policies: disproportionate investment in private ventures and tourism, and the absence of a public housing policy.

Territory

Portugal
Lisbon, Mouraria

[23] This review is based on research by Simone Tulumello of Habita65 - Associação pelo direito à habitação e à cidade / Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon, Portugal, and Giovanni Allegretti of the University of Coimbra, Portugal / University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa.

Aerial photograph of the Mouraria neighborhood located in the center of Lisbon. Map: Google; images: DigitalGlobe, IGP/DGRF, 2024.

The current urban transformation observed in many southern European cities must therefore be understood as the articulation of several processes, including gentrification, touristification and financialisation. This case offers important analytical and strategic insights for research on urban change in Southern Europe and, more broadly, for global urban studies.

Analytically, there are empirical arguments that explain the inadequacy of the concept of gentrification; they suggest that gentrification, touristification (and financialisation) cannot be disentangled and analysed as independent variables of urban transformation; that articulation as a lens through which to observe these processes is necessary because, as mentioned above, it allows these categories to have analytical power in contexts other than those in which they originated.

In strategic terms, the growing evidence of gentrification, touristification and financialisation suggests that southern Europe is moving from being a 'frontier' region of urban theory to becoming a paradigmatic space where new forms of urbanisation-as-accumulation are taking place and, at the same time, where new politics and struggles over the right to the city are emerging.

Participating node

- Habita65 - Associação pelo direito à habitação e à cidade, Portugal

Further information

- Tulumello, Simone; Allegretti, Giovanni (2021). *Articulating urban change in Southern Europe: Gentrification, touristification and financialisation in Mouraria, Lisbon*. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 28(2), 111-132. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969776420963381>

However, while regeneration policies in other central Lisbon neighbourhoods promoted gentrification and touristification, Mouraria took a different path. Until the end of 2014, property prices did not rise, or rose more slowly than in other parts of the city centre, while the influx of young households with relatively low economic but high cultural capital did not lead to displacement; on the contrary, new and old residents formed crucial networks for local development. Mouraria was an 'abnormal' case in terms of typical gentrification trajectories, as regeneration policies did not produce the same gentrification patterns described in other Lisbon neighbourhoods. It subsequently became more of a paradigmatic case within wider processes that have since transformed cities across southern Europe.

Until around 2015, Mouraria was able to halt – and even counteract – gentrification, with some pockets of successful resistance. On the contrary, the neighbourhood was dramatically transformed when gentrification was combined with tourism and financial speculation.

In terms of empirical work, the trajectory of Mouraria was analysed through a longitudinal case study, focusing on two periods close in time to foreground the factors of change: the 'crisis' (2008-2014) and the 'post-crisis' (2015-2019). In both periods, we studied public policy documents, conducted interviews with key actors linked to urban policy-making, descriptive analysis of statistical data (census) and press articles on urban regeneration policies and their effects in Mouraria. Participant observation during mobilisations for the right to the city was used to complement the understanding of political trends and community organisation. Finally, for the thematic analysis, a systematic review of scientific literature on Mouraria published during the "crisis" and "post-crisis" periods was carried out using keywords, with the aim of identifying whether these works take into account the urban change experienced by this area of the city.

Case 15

Fighting for the right to the island in La Tejita, Tenerife, Spain²⁴

Keywords

Right to the island

Right to nature

Island development

Touristification

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

Tourism is an attractive economic growth activity for governments, private companies and international organisations, especially in places on the periphery of global capitalism. This growth strategy has an impact on the transformation of coastal areas and their surroundings, as well as on the enclosure of common spaces. This is the case of the Canary Islands, where tourism is the main economic activity – accounting for 35 per cent of GDP – so its expansion has been a priority for the public authorities since the middle of the 20th century.

The first destinations of mass tourism in the Canary Islands were the two central islands of the archipelago: Tenerife and Gran Canaria. Although it is possible to distinguish different waves in the development of tourism in this region, since 2008 the property and tourism market has undergone a major expansion that has affected most areas of the island, where there has been strong development of infrastructure and mega-projects.

Occupation of the area where the Viqueira company is illegally building the La Tejita hotel, given that it is a land declared to be part of the maritime-terrestrial public domain; the construction is taking place despite the existence of a legal document (escrito de costas) from Madrid stating that this company cannot build in this space. Photograph by César Hernández and Alfonso Boullón, 2024.

Type of accumulation

Rent extractivism, real estate market, touristification

Extended urbanisation and redevelopment; major projects and infrastructures

Territory

Spain

Tenerife, Islas Canarias

Although the relationship between capital and conservation is not new, in recent decades new ways of exploiting nature have emerged. With the accelerated process of urban development based on the construction of infrastructure and specialisation in tourism, large flows of capital have been channelled into real estate in tourist areas to satisfy the desire of the ruling classes to integrate the islands into the world economy (Harvey, 2003, cited by the authors). Indeed, previously protected areas of the Canary Islands have been reclassified as suitable for urbanisation, allowing non-agricultural activities, combined with other initiatives aimed at expanding tourism.

In 2015, the mayor of Granadilla de Abona announced the construction of a luxury hotel – in the south of the island of Tenerife – as a new driving force for tourism and an opportunity to boost job creation. It was to be a five-star hotel, whose final project was approved in 2018, with 883 beds and a surface area of 26,758 m² and 276 linear metres on the beach of La Tejita. However, this large-scale project was illegal: it encroached on the protected coastal strip and had a major negative impact on the fauna, flora and landscape of two protected areas of the European Natura 2000 network.

[24] This review is based on research by Simone Tulumello of Habita65 - Associação pelo direito à habitação e à cidade / Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon, Portugal, and Giovanni Allegretti of the University of Coimbra, Portugal / University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa.

In response to this large-scale project, between the end of 2015 and the beginning of 2016, many activists organised themselves under the slogan "Save La Tejita" to prevent the construction of this hotel; grassroots social movements fought to prevent the construction of this infrastructure in one of the few undeveloped beach areas in the south of Tenerife, on the assumption that the struggle for the right to nature on this specific scale is defended as the "right to the island".

Insularity plays an essential role, not only because of its capacity to territorialise projects, but also because it creates a scale for collective struggles to protect resources or fight specific projects. Experience shows that local communities and populations in island territories traditionally tend to develop a stronger sense of territoriality than communities in continental areas.

The empirical work carried out consisted of interviews with activists involved and participant observation of meetings and demonstrations organised by social movements, as well as analysis of newspaper archives and urban planning documents. The conflict analysis, in turn, showed how nature remains a key factor in the accumulation of capital, and how the struggle to prevent the destruction or degradation of natural assets is a source of opposition to neoliberalism and allows us to think about alternatives for the future.

Participating nodes

- University of La Laguna, Spain
- Leipzig University, Germany

Further information

- Armas Díaz, Alejandro; Sabaté-Bel, Fernando (2022). "Commodification or the Right to the Island: The Struggle Against the Construction of a Hotel in La Tejita, Tenerife." *Island Studies Journal* 17 (2), 214-234. <https://doi.org/10.24043/isj.386>
- Armas Díaz, Alejandro; Sabaté-Bel, Fernando (2024). "Acaparamiento verde y gris en la construcción de infraestructuras en Tenerife (Islas Canarias, España)". *ACME - An International Journal for Critical Geographies* 23 (5).

Demonstration against the illegal construction of the La Tejita hotel in the Montaña Roja Special Nature Reserve; the activity included a 'tourist tour' showing the different absurdities and irregularities of the project. Photography by Alfonso Boullón, 2020.

Specifically, this struggle has been analysed as an expression of the right to the island, which concentrates efforts to protect certain territories and natural resources from commodification in island contexts, where these processes and their excesses are most evident. In the struggle to defend the island, the official discourse of scale and territoriality is challenged by demands for an alternative model of island development. Echoing Clark (2013), the authors argue that the right to the island is not limited to demands for the protection and defence of the landscape, ecosystem and natural and cultural heritage, but that these aspects are part of a broader debate about the model of island development and its implications.

Demonstration organised by the collective Salvar La Tejita to demand compliance with the law and the halting of construction work on the La Tejita hotel. Photograph by Alfonso Boullón, 2021.

Case 16

The Mallolafquenh or Villarrica Lake Basin in Chile²⁵

Keywords

Mallolafquenh river basin

Real estate extractivism

Ecocide

Touristification

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The Mallolafquenh or Villarrica Lake Basin is a territory of ontological occupation that is used in multiple conflicts, ranging from the development of real estate projects in ancestral territories of great Mapuche cultural significance, to the degradation of natural spaces that are a source of biodiversity, with the defence of water being one of the bridges that unites those who understand life as a series of reciprocal relationships.

The indigenous Mapuche communities of the Wallmapu – the territory inhabited by the Mapuche people – the main guardians of ecosystems and water, are experiencing a constant aggression by the State against their ancestral culture, expressed in various forms of displacement and forced dispossession, through the main instrument of capital, which is territorial accumulation.

The methodological strategy to address this problem was to produce an audiovisual documentary, a tool for denunciation, dissemination and awareness-raising. The process began with the identification of three axes-problems related to territorial accumulation:

The socio-environmental conflict over the pollution of Mallolafquenh or Lake Villarrica, as a result of an excess of nutrients caused largely by human activity: real estate speculation is building luxury homes, often illegally, on the shores of the lake,

The tourist overcrowding during the summer, caused by the construction and management of thousands of hotel beds, and

(i)the demographic explosion in the municipality of Pucón, mainly due to climatic migration, which has increased the population by 30% in the last three years.

Type of accumulation

Rent extractivism, real estate market, touristification

Commodification of public space and the commons.

Territory

Chile

Mallolafquenh or Lake Villarrica, Wallmapu basin

Construction of tourist hot springs at the Salto del León waterfall, Pucón. Photography by Left Hand Rotation, 2022.

[25] This review is based on the work of Manuel Sordo and Sara Mateos of Habita65 - Associação pelo direito à habitação e à cidade / Left Hand Rotation Collective, Portugal.

Interviewing members of the Mapuche community Lof Huisca Catrilef in front of the sacred stone Retxikura. Photography by Left Hand Rotation, 2022.

The structure of the plot was based on the conception of the basin as a whole and on the sequential narrative, starting from the everyday to construct the political. We opted for a fluid narrative through being together, as tributaries of the same body of water, trying to conjure up the abyss that Western society has created between human beings and the rest of the living world.

The documentary script was developed through a participatory collective dynamic with local communities, mainly activists from environmental movements and Mapuche indigenous communities, between September and December 2022. It was approached as a first-person plural narrative, opening the process of script construction to the collective in an instantaneous way, allowing the event in front of the camera to cross and modify the way of knowing. The aim was to question the audiovisual language itself, to decentralise the Western epistemic hegemony that analyses, dissects and generates typologies.

This narrative, constructed from interconnected fragments, attempts to recover the Aymara term "ch'ixi" (variegated), proposed by the Bolivian researcher Silvia Rivera Cusicanqui, as a decolonising practice to produce thought from everyday life and construct a narrative that functions as a form of epistemological contestation, since it is a way of telling and communicating that deviates from the linear.

To this end, the 'exquisite corpse', a technique of collective composition in sequence developed by the Surrealists in 1925, was used. They argued that creation should be an anonymous and collective process, spontaneous, playful and as automatic as possible, not guided by reason. This playful technique reveals the unconscious reality of the group that creates it, allowing the non-verbal aspects of conflict and desire to be expressed.

In the construction of this documentary, the application of this technique consisted in each collaborator making a creative contribution conditioned by the contribution of the previous participant and by some pre-agreed rules, linking each contribution as tributaries of the same body of water, collectively constructing a fluid and circular story.

The starting point for the construction of the documentary's narrative axis was the word water. Each participant or collaborator was asked to come up with two words that represented the Villarrica Lake basin. These words were placed in a box and passed on to the next person. In this dynamic, starting with the word water, each participant took a random word out of the box and had to tell a story/poem or whatever they thought connected the previous word and the one they had just taken out of the box. All the stories that form part of the documentary are linked together in a single sequence, beginning and ending with the key word chosen by that community.

Twenty interviews were conducted in a series of one-to-one meetings, recorded from the moment the person took the word out of the box.

The editing of the material also consisted of several collective exchanges to continue the collective construction of the story. All the participants were invited to a working session to complete the scripting process, in which a collective viewing of the resulting sequence was carried out, analysing the chain of words block by block, with the aim of expanding the information potentially contained in each story, unfolding from this backbone the conflicts and resistances contained in the territory, verbalised in the recorded interviews.

Participating node

- Habita65 - Associação pelo direito à habitação e à cidade / Left Hand Rotation, Portugal

Further information

- Documentary feature film La cuenca at <https://www.contested-territories.net/la-cuenca/>

Other documentaries on water disputes

- In Argentina, documentary on the Tigre River
- In Bolivia, documentary on the Katari Basin

Filming Lake Caburga, Pucón. Photography by Left Hand Rotation, 2022.

Case 17

Environmentalisation of conflicts and social policies in disputed territories in the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area, Argentina²⁶

Keywords

Environmentalisation

Spatial appropriation

Relocation

Public policy

Green urban policies

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

This case brings together three research processes located in municipalities of the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires, Argentina, relating to: (i) the implementation of urban developments in coastal areas: riverbanks, floodplains or wetlands, where their proximity to road infrastructure is used to generate extraordinary income, (ii) the implementation of the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin Sanitation Plan, and (iii) the appropriation of urban spaces with agricultural experiences.

They have as a transversal axis the environmentalisation of social conflicts in the context of territorial accumulation projects based on extensive urbanisation, infrastructure construction, the appropriation of common natural goods and the real estate market. Through situated ethnographies, the researchers highlight the different meanings that the actors involved in each process give to concepts such as the environment, natural resources, environmental risk, etc.

Establishment of urban developments in coastal areas

In this research, the empirical work recovers the polysemy of voices pushing for the definition of a problem, demonstrating the process of dispossession associated with urban development, but also the cultural misunderstandings that make it impossible for actors – involved in dynamics of power asymmetry – to reach agreements on the characteristics of the problem and its solutions.

It reveals the tensions between environmental, housing and economic arguments to define the legitimate uses of urban space, and finds that the interests of the most powerful economic actor, the Techint business group, which agrees to the possibility of building a real estate project in the disputed territory, are privileged.

Type of accumulation

Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds, touristification

Extended urbanisation and redevelopment; major projects and infrastructures

Extractivism based on exploitation of natural resources

Territory

[26] This review is based on research by Nela Gallardo Araya, Romina Olejarczyk and Marina Wertheimer of the Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani, University of Buenos Aires, Argentina.

El Trébol neighborhood on the banks of the San Francisco stream in the town of Claypole, Almirante Brown district in the Province of Buenos Aires, Argentina. Photography by Romina Olejarczyk, 2022.

Matanza-Riachuelo Basin Sanitation Plan

The work on the implementation of this plan reconstructs the uses of the concept of environmental risk, which underpins the resettlement of families settled in this basin, specifically in the municipality of Almirante Brown. This concept functions as a tool for decision-making by the state, but also as a native category for state workers and the inhabitants of the basin. Different meanings are at the heart of tensions in the struggle for access to the habitat and occupation of the territory.

The research shows the advance of environmental categories in public discourses and in the configuration of conflicts related to habitat, which become tools for regulating the right to the city and reconfiguring disputed territories, but also arguments that accompany challenges to public policies.

The results of the empirical research consist mainly in the characterisation of "environmental risk" as a category native to the sanitation policy of the Matanza-Riachuelo basin, and in the identification of: (i) the "official version" that guides the implementation of this policy, which relocates the affected population on the basis of territorial criteria such as the towpath and the riverbank line; (ii) the voices of officials and territorial agents, who introduce nuances to this first official version and outline more problematic aspects of this relocation; and (iii) some paradoxical aspects on the part of the affected populations, such as the fact that the very existence of the river is discussed "on paper".

Once again, this research demonstrates the growing use of environmental categories in housing policy, and the existence of official arguments that are contested and reformulated by the actors involved in urban disputes.

Appropriations of urban spaces with agricultural experiences

This research describes a case of dispute over the use of a green space in the city of Buenos Aires, in which environmental arguments operated in two different logics: on the one hand, to give life to a community garden in a disused green space, which sought to decommodify access to food for the population of a Buenos Aires neighbourhood, and on the other, to dismantle it, using arguments of environmental risk linked to the dengue mosquito epidemic. In this way, the green space was replaced by a public promenade which, in the words of the farmers, finally became a "concrete space".

These studies are approached from an anthropological perspective; through ethnography and participant observation, they highlight the polysemy and ambiguity present in social conflicts. From the particularities of each case, they show how economic sectors, real estate agents and the state promote the reconversion of urban spaces contested by popular sectors and social actors.

Despite taking place in different territorial contexts of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area and even with different

social policy intentions, the three cases studied can be interrogated from the perspective of the concept of territorial accumulation and have in common the fact that they have been generated by the environmentalisation of conflicts and social policies.

Public walkway that was built on the site of a garden that operated for almost 10 years, under the argument of "environmental risk"; in the words of the gardeners, the garden was replaced by a "cement space". Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, Argentina. Photograph by Nela Gallardo, 2017.

Although they appear to be very different – the urban regeneration of the Vicente López riverbank, the eradication of vegetable gardens in the city of Buenos Aires and the relocation of settlements in the Matanza-Riachuelo basin – these processes cannot be understood without taking into account the growing role of financial capital, especially real estate, in the production of urban space and its legitimisation through a wide range of environmental arguments.

The dialogue between the three fields of research has made it possible to problematise the use of environmental arguments in the definition of urban policies, which can favour, delay or even reverse the mechanisms of territorial accumulation.

All these studies share the perspective of qualitative research, carried out through ethnographic work, including in-depth interviews, semi-structured interviews, informal conversations, observations with and without participation, and observation tours. It was also based on the analysis of official documents (minutes, resolutions, plans, regulations) and legal files, as well as the review of newspapers and social networks.

Participating node

- Grupo Antropología, Ciudad y Naturaleza del Área de Estudios Urbanos del Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina

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Case 18

Popular habitat vs. gated communities

Contradictions and conflicts in the southern periphery of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area, Argentina ²⁷

Keywords

Popular habitat

Gated communities

Blue and green infrastructure

Public policies

Type of accumulation

Urbanisation, redevelopment, large projects and infrastructures

Commodification of public space and the commons.

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

The urban peripheries in the south of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area are undergoing various processes of dispersed, segregated, fragmented and exclusionary urbanisation for the popular sectors, in which the strategies of large real estate developers in the acquisition and use of land converge with certain public policies related to the requalification of road infrastructure, changes in zoning regulations and the lack of direct land management tools.

A visible result of these processes is the predominance of closed urbanisations for high-income sectors as the social housing modality. Between 2004 and 2020, these will account for 60% of the area of residential expansion in five municipalities in the south of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area: Esteban Echeverría, Almirante Brown, Ezeiza, San Vicente and Presidente Perón.

Territory

Eugenia Larreche crossing the popular neighborhood of El Triunfo, next to the La Sofía stream, in the southern expansion strip of the municipality of Esteban Echeverría, southern zone of the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires. Photography by Ricardo Apaolaza, 2023.

In this scenario, the so-called "Green Corridor Canning - San Vicente" has been created, where this type of urbanisation is expanding in a dispersed manner, and where the construction of public road infrastructure works, such as the Presidente Perón motorway (3rd ring road around Buenos Aires) and the conversion of the Provincial Route 58 into a dual carriageway, as well as changes in the zoning regulations for land use in each of these municipalities, have played a fundamental role.

In contrast, between 2004 and 2020, the popular habitat occupied a much smaller area of the total residential expansion (6% of consolidated urban plots, 17% of unconsolidated plots, 3% of social housing, 7% of informal urbanisation) and was increasingly restricted territorially, even coming into conflict with property developers over land, as happened in the "Guernica conflict" of 2020, in the municipality of Presidente Perón. There, for four months, more than two thousand families occupied around 98 hectares of land subject to real estate

[27] This review is based on research by Jorge Blanco, Ricardo Apaolaza and Juan Pablo Venturini of the University of Buenos Aires, Argentina.

Entrance to the Brickland gated community, on the expansion front of gated communities in the town of Canning, west of the municipality of Esteban Echeverría, southern area of the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires. Photography by Juan Pablo Venturini, 2020.

speculation, in a struggle defended as "land recovery". Part of the land was claimed by a property developer for the construction of a gated community. The conflict resulted in the violent eviction of the families (Venturini, Apaolaza, Ferlicca and Sumiza, 2021). In this study area, there was also a sharp decline in primary land use (decrease in horticulture and brick production).

Territorial accumulation is effectively produced by the relationship between the process of urbanisation and the concentration of economic surplus. In the case studied, this is concretely manifested in the fact that large urban developers make extraordinary profits through the extraction of peri-urban land rents. The "green and blue infrastructure" (wetlands and high-quality green spaces) is mainly used to generate monopoly rents from segregation and environmental amenities, which explains the high prices at which they can market land in gated communities.

Developers are also moving in on land damaged by extractive activities, which they acquire at very low prices. These lands, traditionally occupied by popular sectors, also lose the possibility of being transformed

into green and blue infrastructures, which are beneficial to society as a whole, providing recreational spaces and water regulation to mitigate the effects of floods, which are particularly serious for popular neighbourhoods in the area.

The empirical work was carried out between 2020 and 2023 using various techniques and sources: field visits with photographic surveys; semi-structured interviews with key informants: Real estate agents and developers of closed urbanisations, plots or open subdivisions for popular sectors, periurban primary producers (horticulturists, brick producers) and municipal public officials and from the National Ministry of Transport; Survey of land use per plot in five municipalities (Esteban Echeverría, Almirante Brown, Ezeiza, San Vicente and Presidente Perón) through observation of satellite images (from the Google Earth platform), in order to identify mainly the socio-housing modalities of residential expansion; survey of land prices through real estate web portals and public geo-referenced databases; and processing of the information and elaboration of thematic cartography of land use and prices through open access GIS (QGIS).

Participating node

- Instituto de Geografía de la Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina

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Case 19

People's markets, food consumption and production circuits²⁸

Keywords

Popular markets

Agro-ecology

Food production

Touristification

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

Food today is a terrain of contestation that crosses the entire chain of production, marketing and consumption, involving multiple actors from the family, community and cooperative level to global production and marketing in large supermarket chains. Different actors, capitals, interests, discourses and strategies of action converge on this terrain of contestation.

In this context, critical agri-food studies have been concerned with analysing how the production, distribution and access to food are part of the global capitalist system, through processes of industrialisation and standardisation that promote and reinforce unequal and colonial relations. They also bring to light challenges to these dynamics, proposing alternative mechanisms of production, access and distribution, but also questioning the quality of food, which involves problematising aspects of nutrition and production technologies.

In Europe and Latin America, popular production, trade and market circuits are subject to processes of commodification and neoliberalisation promoted by state and private actors. The territorial scale of these dynamics reveals the production of injustices in rural and urban environments, which are contested by collective organising strategies that propose alternative practices based on agroecological production, fair trade and cooperativism.

A number of studies on the commodification of food production, consumption and marketing circuits have been carried out in Latin American and European countries, particularly in Argentina, Spain and the United Kingdom. A central theme in this issue is the public regulations that shape production, marketing and consumption chains. The creation of such regulations is a central arena of the food debate.

Type of accumulation

Commodification and neo-liberalisation of production and trade circuits and popular markets

Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds, touristification

Territories

Spain

Argentina

United Kingdom

Productive farm in Florencio Varela, province of Buenos Aires, worked by the organization "La 1610", a group of horticultural producers who practice agroecology and sell directly or through solidarity intermediation. Photograph by María Florencia Marcos, 2018.

[28] This review is based on research by Pablo Callegaris and Beatriz Nussbaumer of the University of Buenos Aires, Argentina; Héctor Grad of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain; Sara González of the University of Leeds, UK; María Florencia Marcos and Paula Rosa of the Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales (CEUR-CONICET), Argentina.

In the United Kingdom, traditional retail food markets have undergone major changes since their heyday in the 19th century. Initially, they functioned as community centres focused on ensuring food security and the homogeneity of workers' consumption habits. Since the 1970s, with the dominance of neoliberal ideas, they have been neglected and disinvested, while private capital and public investment has focused on shopping malls and, more recently, online retailing. At the same time, the 'market' for fresh produce is monopolised by five large supermarket chains. Food markets are marginalised and stigmatised because they tend to serve the working class, minority groups and the elderly; today, the 1,000 or so community food markets in the UK have become a residual role in the food distribution chain in terms of revenue generation for local authorities, with no defined social function, while marketing and consumption are dominated by the supermarkets built in the 1990s as part of neoliberal urban planning policies.

In Madrid, the transformation of markets is part of the development plans that aim to integrate the city into the global tourist and financial circuit, building an image of a competitive city with international projection. Local markets are currently contested territories, between traditional retail shops and new gourmet ventures designed for tourism. In the process of gentrification, former food markets have been transformed into spaces for hospitality, leisure and recreation, similar to shopping malls, losing their original social function of providing fresh food. The neoliberal transformation has not been homogeneous, ranging from spaces for catering and gourmet food aimed at the transient population, to spaces that combine traditional food shops with catering, to cases where the market is transformed into a space for urban experimentation that includes alternative market initiatives (such as the commercialisation of local agro-ecological and artisanal production). Alongside these transformations, there are also experiences of resistance to the neoliberal market, such as self-organised chains of direct food production and distribution between producers and consumers.

Assembly of producers, consumers and heads of consumption nodes at the Universidad Nacional de Quilmes, Argentina. Academics, agroecological horticultural producers from Florencio Varela and El Pato (both in the Province of Buenos Aires) and marketers such as Mercado Territorial and Kolmena Oeste participated. Photograph by María Florencia Marcos, 2018.

Consumer groups from Madrid provide their workforce within the framework of a cooperative for consumption, agroecological production and sale of vegetable baskets on a property in La Iglesia del Tiétar, Spain. Photograph by María Florencia Marcos, 2018.

In the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area, neoliberal policies have affected productive concentration markets or supply markets. While in the 1980s a concentrated monopoly market was created, called the "central market", between 1991 and 1993 this centrality was deregulated, giving rise to the free market that continues to this day.

In the AMBA, there are also alternative marketing experiences, developed on the margins among small producers, with the support of academia (especially national public universities) and technical teams from government agencies that have proposed agroecological production alternatives, through a participatory guarantee system (Sistema Participativo de Garantía) based on cooperation and trust. Participation in the system appears to be a strategy for strengthening and making visible this type of small-scale production, as well as a guarantee of quality for consumers.

In the analysis of the circuit of popular markets, the notion of territorial accumulation is used as a theoretical concept, linked to the extractive processes of agribusiness and the transformation of urban spaces for tourist purposes, considering that the production and distribution of food and other consumer goods constitute a fundamental sphere of territorial accumulation and dispossession. But it is also understood that the neoliberal transformation of space implies processes of revaluation (and creative destruction) of commercial spaces and, in markets, even the contestation of space between different projects and models of production-distribution-consumption.

This perspective also makes visible the challenges to the production, marketing and consumption of food from community, agro-ecological and popular forms that seek to modify the distribution market and the social relations between consumers and producers.

The empirical work carried out by different research groups in these areas has been based on qualitative research approaches: semi-structured interviews, participant observation and mapping; ethnographies with agroecological producers' organisations; audiovisual interviews with traders and consumers of agroecological products; literature review.

Old Spitalfields Market in East London, a former food market, is now home to international retail chains and restaurants. Photograph by Sara González, 2024.

Participating nodes

- Facultad de Agronomía y Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales (CEUR-CONICET), Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina
- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain
- University of Leeds, United Kingdom

Further information

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Leeds Market. Photograph by Sara González, 2024.

Case 20

Markets and neighbourhoods against gentrification in Madrid²⁹

Keywords

Popular markets

Agro-ecology

Food production

Touristification

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

Popular markets are undergoing profound transformations in cities affected by the logic of touristification and gentrification. This is the case of Madrid, a city where, in recent decades, traditional markets have been transformed into thematic places of tourist attraction, distinction and leisure for a certain sector of the middle class. However, the question of the markets is part of a broader debate within the framework of development plans that seek to insert the city into the global tourist and financial circuit, under the premise of Madrid as a competitive city with international projection.

As part of the reconversion process, the markets were initially presented by the local government and the business sector as degraded spaces in need of new investment to "modernise and update" them. This discourse was the starting point for transforming their vocation, infrastructure and social function. As a result, markets have been transformed into tourist consumer goods; shops that used to offer basic necessities have been replaced by gourmet services for a transient public with medium or high purchasing power. Territorially, the conflict takes place mainly in the central Alameda neighbourhoods of the city, but also in the former municipal food markets.

This process has been made possible by the implementation of three successive public policies: between 2003 and 2011, the Innovation and Transformation Plan for the Municipal Markets of Madrid (drawn up by the Madrid City Council in 2003); between 2012 and 2015, the same plan was expanded with a focus on marketing and promotion of the Mercados de Madrid brand; finally, in the period 2017-2021, the Strategic Plan for the Municipal Markets of Madrid was implemented, focusing on the physical renovation of the buildings with the financial support of large companies to increase profitability.

Type of accumulation

Commodification and neo-liberalisation of production and trade circuits and popular markets

Rent extractivism, real estate market, investment funds, touristification

Territory

The ethnographic research process included interviews, participant observation, linguistic landscapes and analysis of the discourse of ordinary people and municipal institutions. Digital mapping was used as a tool to systematise and make visible the various transformations of urban spaces, including challenges to their commodification. Through ethnographic research and constant presence in the disputed territories, it has been possible to document the territorial struggle of neighbourhood organisations and social movements in Madrid that demand that priority be given to the housing, health, leisure and supply needs of residents.

[29] This review is based on research by Héctor Grad of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain.

Swing session, an alternative project at the San Fernando market in Madrid. Photography by Gadea Claver, 2021.

The impact of the change in the social function of markets, as well as other commons put at the service of tourism, is contested by neighbourhood organisations and social movements that contest the legitimate uses of public spaces. This research systematises the multiple neoliberal transformations of food markets, such as the San Fernando market (Lavapiés), and the processes of construction of urban commons in self-managed spaces as resistance to neoliberal urbanism; an example of these contests is the creation of a self-managed social centre called "La ingobernable" in spaces occupied as part of the struggle against gentrification and in support of social and popular movements in the city.

Participating node

- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain

Further information

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Case 21

The bio in Berlin³⁰

Keywords

Organic food

Sale-channels

Food production

Case description, research strategy and empirical work

Germany is a country with a long history in organic products, with organisational processes of reference for producer associations and certifiers, and with a very important segment of consumers who are aware of environmental processes, food quality, producers' rights, among other variables linked to food production.

The emergence of "bio" supermarkets as well as chain shops, while offering more affordable prices, are perceived by the interviewees (consumers, producers, traders) as threatening and negative due to their large scale, lack of respect for family producers, mistrust of their quality attributes, and the weakening of traditional marketing spaces such as food fairs.

The documentary short film *Lo bio en Berlín* records different perceptions of organic food in the city of Berlin and especially around its modalities and sales channels. The short film explores how the processes of capital accumulation impact on agri-food systems and intensify commodification in the so-called alternative segments such as "organic". The alternative in this case refers to the fact that the production processes differ from the hegemonic model based on the artificialisation of food, that is, on the separation of food from its productive origins and producing subjects; they do not aim for industrialisation, avoid hyper-concentration of different links in the value chain and opt for a type of production focused on environmental sustainability.

Type of accumulation

Commodification and neo-liberalisation of production and trade circuits and popular markets

Territory

Organic food stall at the market on Winterfeldtplatz in Berlin. Photography by Beatriz Nussbaumer, 2022.

[30] This review is based on research by Carlos Cowan Ros of the Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET) and Beatriz Nussbaumer of the University of Buenos Aires, Argentina.

Beatriz Nussbaumer and Carlos Cowan from CEUR-CONICET, Argentina, on a documentary interview exercise at the Torero Films Summer Lab in Berlin. Photography by Rouven Rech, 2022.

Buenos Aires in 2025. A qualitative methodology was applied, based on participant observation, visits to the different sales channels and interviews with producers and consumers using audiovisual equipment. A previously elaborated dossier, with the structure, narrative aspects and other audiovisual elements, guided its construction. The functioning of five markets (weekly fairs operating in squares) where organic products are sold was recorded in video, notes and photographs; different supermarkets were visited and images were recorded in different formats. The notion of territorial accumulation structured the fieldwork, the exploration of the issues and the interviews.

Participating node

- Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales (CEUR-CONICET) / Facultad de Agronomía de la Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina

Further information

- Documentary short film "Lo bio in Berlin". <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s9SpGBEeLdQ>

Other products under development

- Documentary short film "Lo bio en Madrid" (in editing stage)
- Documentary short film "Lo bio en Buenos Aires" (in production stage)

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Generating plural and participatory knowledge

The empirical work carried out by CONTESTED_TERRITORY with the objective of accounting for the processes of territorial accumulation present in different territories, has been carried out from a diversity of methodological strategies, including experimental methodologies and with a strong emphasis on participatory processes.

Documentary and historical review, research of multiple sources of printed and audiovisual material; interviews, accompaniment, participation in instances of resistance, struggle and debate; training and exchange of knowledge with local actors; representation tasks; performance, creation, construction of materialities; and a lot of observation and silence are part of the devices used in these investigations.

In the construction of knowledge, contributions and perspectives have come from diverse practices and understandings, integrating different forms of knowledge: those of academia, activism and local communities. Empirical research has had a strong focus on the co-production of knowledge and has sought interaction with local actors as an objective.

Overall, the work carried out by CONTESTED_TERRITORY is ascribed to militant research, based on collaborative knowledge production and recognizing that only plural and inclusive empirical research can account for spatial, territorial, climatic and social injustices and generate alternatives for interpretation and action, and in this way effectively contribute to the struggle to reverse them.

